

HORIZON 2020

The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation

Methodology review and selection

Deliverable D1.3

DATE

31 July 2020

ISSUE

1.0

GRANT AGREEMENT

no 870337

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU

PROJECT WEB-SITE

<http://cure-copernicus.eu/>

LEAD AUTHOR

Wieke Heldens (DLR)

CO-AUTHORS

Elisabeth Brzoska (DLR)
Alessandra Gandini (Tecnalia)
Laura Gutierrez (Tecnalia)
Efren Feliu (Tecnalia)
Maidar Arana (Tecnalia)
Mattia Marconcini (DLR)
Annekatriin Metz-Marconcini (DLR)
Zina Mitraka (FORTH)

CONTENTS

List of Figures	4
List of Tables.....	4
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Purpose of the document	5
1.2 Related files	5
1.3 Definitions and acronyms	5
2 Background	8
3 Methodology	10
4 App 01 - Local Scale Surface Temperature Dynamics.....	10
4.1 Description of CURE App.....	10
4.2 Summary of state of the art methods	11
4.3 Relevant EU projects	13
4.4 Potential benchmark for CURE	13
5 App 02 - Surface Urban Heat Island Assessment.....	14
5.1 Description of CURE App.....	14
5.2 Summary of State of the Art methods.....	14
5.3 Relevant EU projects	15
5.4 Potential benchmark for CURE	15
6 App 03 - Urban Heat Emissions Monitoring.....	16
6.1 Description of CURE App.....	16
6.2 Summary of state of the art methods	16
6.3 Relevant EU projects	17
6.4 Potential benchmark for CURE	17
7 App 04 - Urban CO2 Emissions Monitoring.....	17
7.1 Summary of state of the art methods	18
7.2 Relevant EU projects	19
7.3 Potential benchmark for CURE	19
8 App 05 - Urban Flood Risk	19

8.1	Description of CURE App.....	19
8.2	Summary of state of the art methods	21
8.3	Relevant EU projects	24
8.4	Potential benchmark for CURE	26
9	App 06 - Urban Subsidence, Movements and Deformation Risk	26
9.1	Description of CURE App.....	26
9.2	Summary of state of the art methods	27
9.3	Relevant EU projects	28
9.4	Potential benchmark for CURE	29
10	App 07 - Urban Air Quality.....	29
10.1	Description of CURE App.....	29
10.2	Summary of state of the art methods	30
10.3	Relevant EU projects	31
10.4	Potential benchmark for CURE	31
11	App 08 - Urban Thermal Comfort.....	32
11.1	Description of CURE App.....	32
11.2	Summary of state of the art methods	32
11.3	Relevant EU projects	33
11.4	Potential benchmark for CURE	34
12	App 09 - Urban Heat Storage Monitoring	34
12.1	Description of CURE App.....	34
12.2	Summary of state of the art method	34
12.3	Relevant EU projects	35
12.4	Potential benchmark for CURE	35
13	App 10 - Nature Based Solutions.....	35
13.1	Description of CURE App.....	35
13.2	Summary of state of the art methods	36
13.3	Relevant EU projects	37
13.4	Potential benchmark for CURE	39
14	App 11 - Health Impacts (socioeconomic perspective)	39
14.1	Description of CURE App.....	39

14.2	Summary of state of the art methods	40
14.3	Relevant EU projects	41
14.4	Potential benchmark for CURE	41
15	References	42

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Conceptual illustration of CURE (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe) development as a cross-cutting structure, based on products derived from four different Copernicus Core Services: CLMS, CAMS, C3S and EMS. The CURE system will be built on Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) and will contain cross-cutting applications related to urban resilience, reflecting urban sustainability dimensions.	9
Figure 2 Baseline design of the LST downscaling methodology, adapted from Mitraka et al. (2015) CLMS and CAMS provide information on urban surface cover and atmosphere, respectively.)	11
Figure 3 Baseline design of the Urban Flood Risk Service	20
Figure 4 Classification scheme of modeling methodologies (Nkwunonwo et al., 2020)	21
Figure 5 Processing architecture for global flood monitoring using S-1 SAR image data (Matgen et al., 2020).....	24

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Required data for urban flood analysis	22
---	----

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document, Deliverable 1.3, is the result of Task 1.4 of WP1. It provides a review of current methodologies which can be of use in the implementation of the proof-of-concept/prototype (as well as for benchmarking activities) for each intended CURE application. Here, major focus is given to previous FP7 and H2020 projects, especially those addressing urban resilience topics.

1.2 Related files

This document is accompanied by a spreadsheet, which contains the results of the literature review in a comparable and tabulated way. The file is named "[CURE D1.3 Methodology review and selection.xls](#)".

1.3 Definitions and acronyms

App	CURE Application
ARM	Aerodynamic Resistance Method
ASTER	Advanced SPaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CAR	Complete Apect Ratio
CCA	City Clustering Algorithm
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
c_p	heat capacity
CURE	Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe
DALY	Disability Adjusted Life Year
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
E_B	emissions from combustion within buildings
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting
EMS	Emergency Management Service
EO	Earth Observation
ESTM	Element Surface Temperature Method
ETM+	Enhanced Thematic Mapper

EU	European Union
Ev	emissions from fossil fuel combustion by motor vehicles
EVA	Economic Evaluation of Air Pollution
F _c	net CO ₂ flux
FP7	7th Framework Programm (EU funding programm)
GHG	Green House Gas
GIS	Geo-Information System
H2020	Horizon 2020 (EU funding program)
HR	High Resolution
InSAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry
LSE	Land Surface Emissivity
LUMPS	Local scale Urban Meteorological Parameterization Scheme
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MOST	Monin-Obukhov similarity theory
MSI	Multispectral Instrument
MWA	Mono-WInDow-Algorithm
NBS	Nature Based Solution
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
OGC	Open GIS Consortium
OHM	Objective Hysteresis Model
OLCI	Ocean and Land Colour Instrument
PET	Physiologically Equivalent Temperature
PIS	Percentage Impervious Surface
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
PS	Persistent (or permanent) Scatterers
PSI	Persistent Scatterer Interferometry
PT	Perceived Temperature
P _v	CO ₂ assimilation by photosynthesis
Q*	net radiation
Q _E	latent heat flux
RES	Energy Balance Residual method
r _H	bulk aerodynamic resistance for heat
R _H	metabolic release of CO ₂ by human respiration
RI	Research Infrastructure
R _s	below ground soil root and waste microbial respiration
RTE	Radiative Transfer Equation
R _v	above ground vegetation respiration

RWE	Real World Evidence
SAR	synthetic aperture radar
SCA	Single Channel Algorithm
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
SUHI	Surface Urban Heat Island
SUHII	Surface Urban Heat Island Intensity
SWA	Split Window Algorithm
T_0	aerodynamic surface temperature
T_a	dry bulb (ambient) temperature
T_A	air temperature
TEB	Town Energy Balance
T_g	black globe temperature
TIR	Thermal Infrared
TIRS	Thermal Infrared Sensor
TM	Thematic Mapper
TMS	Thermal Mass Scheme
TOA	Top of Atmosphere
T_R	radiative surface temperature
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
TSI	Thermal Satellite Imagery
T_w	natural wet bulb temperature
UCL	Urban Canopy Layer
UEB	Urban Energy Budget
UHI	Urban Heat Island
UHII	Urban Heat Island Intensity
UTCI	Universa Thermal Climate Index
VNIR	Visible and Near-Infrared
WBGT	wet bulb globe temperature
WHO	World Health Organisation
ΔQ_s	heat storage
ρ	air density
Q_H	turbulent sensible heat flux

2 BACKGROUND

Resilience has become an important necessity for cities, particularly in the face of climate change. Urban resilience refers to the ability of an urban system to maintain or rapidly return to desired functions in the face of a disturbance, to adapt to change, and to quickly transform systems that limit current or future adaptive capacity (Meerow et al., 2016). Mitigation and adaptation actions that enhance the resilience of cities need to be based on a sound understanding and quantification of the drivers of urban transformation and settlement structures, human and urban vulnerability, and of local and global climate change, as defined in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the New Urban Agenda (UN, 2015, UN, 2017). Copernicus, as the means for the establishment of a European capacity for Earth Observation (EO), is based on continuously evolving Core Services. A major challenge for the EO community is the innovative exploitation of the Copernicus products in dealing with the multidimensional problem of urban sustainability towards increasing urban resilience. Due to multidimensional nature of urban resilience, to meet this challenge, information from more than one Copernicus Core Services, namely the Land Monitoring Service (CLMS), the Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), the Climate Change Service (C3S) and the Emergency Management Service (EMS), the Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) and the Copernicus service for Security applications, is needed. Furthermore, to address urban resilience, the urban planning community needs spatially disaggregated environmental information at local (neighbourhood) and city scales. Such information, for all parameters needed, is not yet directly available from the Copernicus Core Services mentioned above, while several elements - data and products - from contemporary satellite missions consist valuable tools for retrieving urban environmental parameters at local scale. Therefore, to address urban resilience, cross-cutting applications among the above Copernicus Core Services are needed, which should also be capable of coping with the required scale and granularity by also integrating or exploiting third-party data, in-situ observations and modelling. The project CURE (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe) will provide the means to cope with the EO data under-exploitation in the domain of sustainable and resilient urbanization, by combining products of different Copernicus Core Services, as shown in **Figure 1**. CURE will therefore enable Copernicus to better serve cross-cutting applications at European scale by introducing novel ideas on how applications for climate change adaptation and mitigation, healthy cities and social environments, as well as energy and economy will be developed across Copernicus Core Services.

The main goal of CURE is to demonstrate the potential of Copernicus to provide valuable information for urban resilience, supported by third-party data and in-situ observations, as appropriate. The main research question addresses whether and to what extent the Copernicus Core Services are able to provide reliable information for enhancing the resilience of European cities. CURE will answer this question by developing cross-cutting applications

combining products from four different Copernicus Core Services (i.e., CLMS, CAMS, C3S and EMS) with third-party data (e.g., in-situ measurements, street-view imagery, socio-economic data).

CURE is expected to demonstrate the technical operational feasibility of an umbrella of 11 cross-cutting applications on urban resilience. These applications make use of Copernicus core products from at least two Core Services each as main input information and are relevant to the user needs, since strong stakeholders' involvement is foreseen. As the sustainable development is a cornerstone for European Union policies (i.e., EU Strategy for Sustainable Development; 7th Environmental Action Plan; Thematic Strategies on urban environment, energy and sustainable use of resources; 20-20-20 targets; targets of the 2030 Energy Strategy), the chosen applications are relevant to European Union policies and to SDGs (especially to SDG 11). Synergies among different investigation methods (in-situ measurements, modelling and remote sensing) will enable scientific and pre-operational validation and benchmarking to demonstrate the technical feasibility, the level of maturity and the scientific value of the intended CURE applications. It will also be used to fill the existing gap in current Copernicus offer in relation to urban areas and help to investigate if new observation requirements for space-borne instruments are needed to realise or improve the chosen applications.

This document supports the scientific and pre-operational validation and benchmarking. Specifically, it provides an overview of the state of the art approaches more relevant for each CURE application (App).

Figure 1 Conceptual illustration of CURE (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe) development as a cross-cutting structure, based on products derived from four different Copernicus Core Services: CLMS, CAMS, C3S and EMS. The CURE system will be built on Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) and will contain cross-cutting applications related to urban resilience, reflecting urban sustainability dimensions.

3 METHODOLOGY

The focus of the literature review in this document is on relevant methodologies for the CURE Apps. In the literature and especially also in past EU projects (e.g. FP7 and H2020 funded projects) it is searched for common, well-established or otherwise suitable methodologies and services that can serve as a benchmark for the CURE Apps.

After an introduction to each CURE App and the corresponding envisaged methodologies, existing approaches identified in the literature are briefly described in the state of the art section. Then, related past and present EU projects are presented, which often developed methodologies with a high technical readiness level (TRL) and advanced implementations of Copernicus Services. Each CURE App chapter is concluded by a short discussion on the available methodologies to be possibly used as benchmark in the project. Additionally, an XLS table is created for each App, where the main approaches are described and their main features are gathered and listed in a comparative way. These include for instance information on: input data, areas and time for which the method was applied or could be applied, validation results, as well as the number of citations or downloads to assess the acceptance in the community. Additionally, it is also indicated whether the method is available to the CURE project (e.g. by downloadable code) or not.

4 APP 01 - LOCAL SCALE SURFACE TEMPERATURE DYNAMICS

Land surface temperature (LST) is an important indicator associated with climatic, meteorological, hydrological and environmental phenomena and processes that is used in several environmental fields such as climate change investigation, hydrological process modelling, drought monitoring, and fire risk assessment (Yang et al., 2020). However, as from the literature, currently the main application of LST is the calculation of Surface Urban Heat Island (SUHI) (see section 5).

There are many factors that influence the LST, such as land surface type, land surface cover, surface moisture, atmospheric conditions, etc. For this reason, it is difficult to obtain in-situ LST measurements that are representative of large areas and, for this reason, in the past four decades the scientific community has developed numerous LST retrieval algorithms from satellite thermal infrared (TIR) remote sensing data. These methods have the advantage of wide coverage and the ability to perform regular revisits of a site.

4.1 Description of CURE App

The LST downscaling approach developed in URBANFLUXES (Mitraka et al., 2015, Mitraka and Doxani, 2016) will be used in CURE to develop the Local Scale Surface Temperature Dynamics application. In particular, atmospheric information from C3S and surface cover information from CLMS will be used (**Figure 1**). Existing CLMS LST assumes the land surface to be

composed of vegetation and bare soil and delivers LST at 5 km spatial resolution. Nevertheless, when referring to the temperature of cities it is important to have local scale LST (i.e., at 100m spatial resolution) derived accounting for the urban surface as well. To this purpose, the LST downscaling approach envisaged in CURE is based on the Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 synergy and it is capable of providing surface temperature estimates at local scale at the frequency of Sentinel 3. The common spectral bands shared in Multispectral Instrument (MSI) of Sentinel 2 and Ocean and Land Colour Instrument (OLCI) and Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (SLSTR) of Sentinel 3 provide the basis for this synergy. The fractions of surface cover types will be quantified using the MSI and OLCI common bands and CLMS data.

The method will be improved in the framework of CURE by adapting it to Copernicus Core Services and it is expected to give coherent LST estimates across all cities. Surface cover information at high spatial resolution is used to downscale the low resolution TIR radiance to simulate a high resolution TIR band. Surface cover information (land cover, vegetation indices and soil moisture) as derived from CLMS, will be combined with fractional surface cover retrievals (Sentinel 2) and spectral libraries (Kotthaus et al., 2014) to estimate surface emissivity (Mitraka et al., 2015, Mitraka et al., 2012). By combining the high resolution TIR and emissivity with atmospheric information from CAMS in a split window algorithm (Jimenez-Munoz et al., 2014) local scale LST will be estimated, as per Mitraka et al. (2015). The downscaled LST values will be evaluated with in-situ radiometric surface temperature observations from the micrometeorological towers in Heraklion and transferred to all case studies (both front runner and follower cities).

Figure 2 Baseline design of the LST downscaling methodology, adapted from Mitraka et al. (2015) CLMS and CAMS provide information on urban surface cover and atmosphere, respectively.).

4.2 Summary of state of the art methods

LST is one of the most vital data recorded by satellites in the recent decades because, as mentioned above, thermal satellite imagery (TSI) offers great potential to improve its understanding (Ndossi and Avdan, 2016). Over the last few decades, advancements of remote sensing along with spatial science have considerably increased the number and

quality of LST and SUHI related studies. Zhou et al. (2019) carried out a systematic review of around 500 works of this type, from their origin in 1972 to the present. Among the conclusions of this research it is important to highlight on the one hand, the exponentially increasing trend of these researches since 2005 and on the other hand, that the two most commonly-used satellite sensors are the Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM)/Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+)/Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) with the 53% of the total publications and Terra/Aqua Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) with 25% of the total publications. A minor proportion of around 7% can be contributed to the Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER).

Most of the scientific literature reviewed, proposes methods or algorithms aimed at reconstructing high-resolution LST time series from the TSI, normally from MODIS or Landsat. As pointed out before, the main advantage is the wide spatial coverage offered by satellite imagery; however, these methods can only reconstruct cloud-free days LST values but not cloudy ones (Kang et al., 2018). For this reason, most studies present results of LST from TSI for a certain day or a certain period of past time.

Regarding the spatial resolution, there are big differences among different studies. For example, the LST from MODIS ranges from 250 m for continental Europe (Metz et al., 2014, Ward et al., 2016) to 90 m in a study performed over China (Kang et al., 2018). The resolutions provided by the studies based on LANDSAT are higher and vary between 90m in a study carried out in four cities in USA (Logan et al., 2020) and 30m in a study developing a QGIS (Ndossi and Avdan, 2016). The latter works with algorithms such as the Mono-Window Algorithm (MWA), the Single Channel Algorithm (SCA), the Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE) and the Plank Equation, which have been implemented in the plugin. In addition to the algorithms, the plugin has an ability to estimate Land Surface Emissivity (LSE), calculating the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), calculating Top of Atmosphere (TOA) radiance and brightness temperature. Both types of studies, either using LANDSAT or MODIS, normally use the same input data, being Land Cover Data, NDVI, DEM and meteorological information.

In the frame of URBANFLUXES project, Mitraka et al. (2015) developed a method that unmixes the low-resolution satellite thermal infrared (TIR) from MODIS measurements using high resolution spatial information from VNIR sensors from LANDSAT for estimating high spatial resolution LST. This approach has a high potential to be operationally used for exploiting the Copernicus Sentinel (2 and 3) observations and providing high spatio-temporal resolution LST estimates in cities, which is exactly what is planned for CURE. This study was applied in Heraklion (Greece) and can be used for daily LST retrieval at the local scale with a resolution of 90m.

Regarding studies that use Copernicus products for LST estimation, for example Yang et al. (2020) adjust 17 well-established Split-window algorithms (SWAs) for estimating LST from Sea

and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (SLSTR) data from Sentinel-3. The results of the algorithms have been validated in: Arou (China), Daman (China), Huazhaizi (China), Huangmo (China), Gobabeb (Namibia) and Lake Constance (Germany) in different days of 2017 and 2018 depending on the place. The results have been produced at 1 km resolution. The training and sensitivity analysis showed that nine of the seventeen SWAs had both good training accuracy and low sensitivity.

Finally, another method to estimate LST is through meso-scale models such as WFR or Urbclim (De Ridder et al., 2015), developed at VITO. It is worth mentioning Urbclim as a model to calculate LST because it will also be used in the thermal comfort App of CURE (see Section 11). Urbclim is a fast boundary-layer urban climate model which makes use of existing Copernicus data such as the CLMS land cover, soil sealing/imperviousness and NDVI for model configuration and surface specification and for climate forcing data is taken from C3S ERA5 re-analysis data. The main advantage of models comparing with the abovementioned TIR is that the former allows LST estimation with climate change projections available in the C3S of Copernicus and with a spatial resolution of 100m.

García-Diéz et al. (2016) compare the LST obtained from Urbclim, WRF and MODIS and compare them with in situ observation of the city of Barcelona. Among the conclusions it is worthy to mention that UrbClim reproduces correctly the LST of Barcelona when it is nested to the coarse dataset of ERA-Interim, while it suffers from a general warm bias. When it is nested to a higher-resolution model (ECMWF IFS), UrbClim additionally reproduces well the temperature evolution of the individual rural and urban stations used for the calculation of the UHI. WRF is less biased than the UrbClim run nested in ERA-Interim, and both runs show comparable skill in reproducing the UHI. Finally, the spatial pattern of LST is similar in UrbClim and WRF, even though significant biases are found in both models when they are evaluated against MODIS data. In conclusion, UrbClim has been found to be well suited urban environment largely depends on the type of variable and process that is to be analyzed.

4.3 Relevant EU projects

The EU-funded project [URBANFLUXES](#) (H2020, 2015 – 2017) addressed the challenge of combating heat in cities' by using EO to identify urban energy budget (UEB) spatial patterns. The consortium successfully developed a method capable of deriving UEB from current and future EO systems based on data from the Copernicus programme's Sentinels missions.

4.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

The methodologies available in the papers reviewed are useful as a benchmark for the LST calculation in the frame of CURE project. All the methodologies described in the corresponding papers and they are based on free and available data, except meso-scale model Urbclim. In this case, the model will be used in the frame of CURE for the development of other Apps and as a consequence it will be considered for comparisons with LST data

obtained in CURE. Besides, the methods described on the papers provide spatial resolutions high enough to describe the LST at a city scale.

5 APP 02 - SURFACE URBAN HEAT ISLAND ASSESSMENT

5.1 Description of CURE App

A reliable characterization of urban heat island (UHI) can contribute to the effective evaluation of potential heat risk; indeed, warmer air caused by UHI increases heat load stress of urban residents, potentially raising the threat of mortality. Moreover, higher temperature increases energy consumption and associated greenhouse gas emissions due to the use of air conditioning. In this framework, to describe the UHI effect, the so-called UHI intensity (UHII) is measured, which is defined as the difference in temperature between urban and surrounding rural regions. Traditionally, the quantification of UHII is conducted at two fixed in-situ stations, one in urban and the other in rural regions; similarly, the study of the surface UHII (SUHII) using remote sensing data is conducted over selected pixels that are located in the urban and rural regions, separately. However, on the one hand fixed pixels only reflects part of the SUHI characteristics (especially in those cities with multiple UHI centers) and solely represent the micro-climate of the local area which they refer to. On the other hand, the different definitions of urban/rural regions make the inter-comparison study of SUHII among different cities particularly challenging. To overcome these limitations, the methodology recently presented by Li et al. (2018) will be used in CURE. In particular, the intended approach will allow calculating SUHII (and its temporal dynamics) by exploiting the relationship between LST and the Percentage Impervious Surface (PIS), which – according to the literature - proved consistent for cities in biomes dominated by forests and grasslands as in Europe.

5.2 Summary of State of the Art methods

In addition to the method of Li et al. (2018), many other approaches exist to quantify the SUHII. In the review paper of Zhou et al. (2019) methodologies for SUHI mapping are reviewed. Mapping of LST is an important part. This topic is addressed in section 4 on AP01. The literature reviewed in Zhou et al. (2019) on SUHII mapping uses mainly the difference between the average LST of urban pixels and rural pixels. Differences between the studies result mainly in how the rural pixels are defined, e.g. based on land cover or using a buffer zone around the urban pixels. An example of this classic approach is the study of Wang et al. (2018). Schwarz et al. (2011) compared 11 methods for quantifying SUHII in 263 European cities using MODIS LST and LC products. The methods include “classic” approaches using the difference between urban and rural pixels, as well as advanced quantification techniques more independent of pre-defined land cover such as Gaussian area or magnitude or Hot Island Area (Schwarz et al., 2011).

The SUHII mapping method by Li et al. (2018) uses the regression coefficient of the linear regression between PIS and LST as indicator for the SUHII, this way avoiding a decision on where the urban area ends and the rural area begins. This approach results in one intensity number per city, as do the methods tested in Schwarz et al. (2011). A method that is also comparable among cities and avoid mapping of urban and rural areas a priori is the SUHI index introduced by Mathew et al. (2016), (Sultana and Satyanarayana, 2020). This intensity measure uses the local pixel LST normalized by the minimum and maximum LST within the AOI and is therefore most suitable to identify hot spots.

Zhou et al. (2017) calculate the SUHI classically by the difference between rural and urban surface temperatures. They use urban morphological zones to define urban areas and then apply the City Clustering Algorithm (CCA) (Rozenfeld et al., 2011). According to CCA, any pair of urban cells with a distance no larger than the cluster parameter I is assigned to the same urban cluster. An equal-area belt region around an identified city cluster is defined as its rural or suburban reference, devoid of water courses and urban pixels of other clusters. The surface UHI intensity of an urban cluster is defined as the difference between average urban (T_c) and rural (T_b) temperature:

$$\Delta T = T_c - T_b$$

Zhou et al. (2017) base their analysis on temporally aggregated temperature data, namely multi-annual summer mean LST.

5.3 Relevant EU projects

In EU projects SUHII mapping has not often been included yet. In the H2020 project [ESMERALDA](#) (H2020 2015 – 2018) a non-remote sensing approach using simulation results to estimate the temperature was developed (Lauwaet et al., 2018).

5.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

The different approaches tested in Schwarz et al. (2011) are interesting to compare the SUHI results of CURE to. As this study covers many European cities, also some of the CURE frontrunner and follower cities will be available. However, only the results published in the paper are available, no code or software. If the method of Li et al. (2018) is implemented, the values derived for the CURE cities should be compared with the values derived in the publication. Of course, the landscape and climatological differences should be accounted for.

6 APP 03 - URBAN HEAT EMISSIONS MONITORING

6.1 Description of CURE App

Urban heat emission refers to the heat exchange between the urban surface and the atmosphere, namely the turbulent sensible heat flux (Q_H). It is strongly modified by the specific properties of the urban surface, i.e., 3D geometry, high roughness, impervious surfaces, complex source/sink distribution and injections of heat and water into the urban atmosphere by human activities (traffic, heating, waste management, etc.). CURE will implement the Aerodynamic Resistance Method - ARM (Voogt and Grimmond, 2000) to estimate Q_H at local scale, following the most advanced methodologies for determining the aerodynamic resistance parameterization.

6.2 Summary of state of the art methods

Turbulent heat flux (exchange) can be modelled by computational fluid dynamics or numerical simulation models or estimated by the bulk transfer approach (Yang et al., 2019). The estimation of sensible heat flux with remote sensing data is based on the bulk transfer approach (Yang et al., 2019), where the surface temperature is derived from satellite data. An implementation of the bulk transfer method is ARM (Voogt and Grimmond, 2000), which is used in several microscale urban climate models like e.g. TUF-3D (Yang et al., 2019).

ARM uses the Monin-Obukhov similarity theory (MOST) (e.g. Foken, 2006) as the theoretical basis to estimate momentum and scalar fluxes in the atmospheric surface layer. MOST is commonly used in meteorological numerical modeling systems. In the MOST framework, roughness lengths for momentum and heat (z_m and z_h , respectively) are the key parameters identifying the aerodynamic features of underlying surfaces (Kanda et al., 2007).

ARM is a common approach for modelling surface fluxes. Q_H is basically calculated as

$$Q_H = c_p \rho \frac{T_0 - T_A}{r_H}$$

where c_p is the heat capacity of the air ($J \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), ρ is the air density (kg m^{-3}), T_0 is the aerodynamic surface temperature (K), T_A is the air temperature (K) and r_H is the bulk aerodynamic resistance for heat (s m^{-1}) of the complete 3D urban surface (Crawford et al., 2018). T_0 is difficult to measure and is often replaced with the satellite-observed LST, the radiative surface temperature (T_R) calculated from measurements of upwelling long wave radiation, or area-weighted facet-based complete surface temperatures from some combination of thermal camera measurements and 3D surface models (Crawford et al., 2018). Using the radiative surface temperature instead of T_0 requires the completion of r_H with a radiometric excess resistance (Voogt and Grimmond, 2000).

The Local scale Urban Meteorological Parameterization Scheme (LUMPS) (Grimmond and Oke, 2002) provides a simple and easy to apply alternative to ARM and consists of a series of linked equations that allow the storage (ΔQ_s), turbulent sensible (Q_H), and latent (Q_E) heat fluxes to be calculated. The basic premise is that heat fluxes can be modeled using net all-wave radiation, simple information on surface cover (areas of vegetation, buildings, and impervious materials), morphometry (roughness element height and density), and standard weather observations (air temperature, humidity, wind speed, and pressure) (Grimmond and Oke, 2002).

6.3 Relevant EU projects

In the [URBANFLUXES](#) project (H2020 2015-2019) a methodology estimating all terms for the UEB has been developed. The developed methods were validated by in-situ measurements. The approach for estimating turbulent heat flux is published in Feigenwinter et al. (2018) and makes use of ARM.

6.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

Cross-comparisons with the respective URBANFLUXES products (Chrysoulakis et al., 2018) could be carried out. These are based on more detailed input data provided by city authorities instead of using input data from Copernicus services, as required in CURE.

7 APP 04 - URBAN CO₂ EMISSIONS MONITORING

The total urban CO₂ emissions have a spatial dimension due to the heterogeneous nature of urban land use/land cover and urbanization. In this CURE App, the CO₂ emissions are partitioned into an anthropogenic (traffic, heating/cooling) and a biogenic component (urban green space). Spatial planning strategies have an influence on the urban form, and consequently affect CO₂ emissions through changes in traffic patterns, energy consumption and location and extent of urban green areas. Knowing the portion of the anthropogenic and the biogenic part of CO₂ emissions in a high spatial resolution (neighborhood scale) will provide urban planners with an additional decision support tool for developing emission reduction strategies.

The approach for estimating within urban boundaries' CO₂ emissions (excluding industrial processes) will be based on statistical modelling of all individual source and sink processes in the urban environment, according to the following equation:

$$F_C = E_V + E_b + R_H + R_S + (R_V - P_V)$$

where, F_c is the net CO_2 flux, E_v concerns emissions from fossil fuel combustion by motor vehicles, E_B is emissions from combustion within buildings (e.g., for heating), R_H is the metabolic release of CO_2 by human respiration, R_s is the below-ground soil, root, and waste microbial respiration, R_v is the above-ground vegetation respiration, and P_v is the CO_2 assimilation by photosynthesis. The method will combine local scale CO_2 flux measurements by Eddy Covariance with geospatial information of urban form parameters through analytic source area modelling (Crawford and Christen, 2014, Stagakis et al., 2019). Turbulent flux source area model will be applied (Kljun et al., 2015) and parameterized based on detailed urban morphology indicators. The relationships between land cover types, land uses, building morphology, population density and the measured F_c will be defined through multiple regression analyses. Traffic profiles from the cities' inventories and air temperature will be auxiliary parameters for E_v and E_B modelling. R_H model will be based on spatially aggregated population statistics (Christen et al., 2011). The different biogenic processes (R_s , R_v , R_s) will be modelled according to established process-based algorithms (Leuning and Kelliher, 1995, Thornley and Johnson, 2000) accounting for environmental controls on photosynthesis and respiration and the analytic vegetation and soil cover and morphology. Individual models will be scaled up to the urban boundaries, reaching daily to monthly local scale city-wide maps, and then synthesized to net CO_2 flux products.

7.1 Summary of state of the art methods

The concentration of atmospheric CO_2 has a significant influence on global warming in which, urban areas play a major role, being responsible for approximately 70% of total CO_2 emissions. In order to monitor its variations and to better understand the multiple emission sources and sinks, several data sets have been used (Jiang and Yung, 2019).

Cities are becoming aware of the importance of having local emission inventories, traditionally developed by using bottom-up approaches based on monthly or annual statistics. Due to the nature and morphology of the urban ecosystem, quantification of CO_2 emissions in urban areas has been challenging. Kennedy et al. (2010) have developed a comparative study of GHG emission in several cities, highlighting the inconsistencies between cities in determining and quantifying inventories, the problems in defining spatial and temporal scales and a lack of life cycle perspective.

Eddy Covariance technique has been widely used in calculating CO_2 exchanges in natural and agricultural ecosystems, but its application in urban areas still remains less common, especially due to the difficulties to find an appropriate location in terms of land cover homogeneity (Helfter et al., 2016, Liu et al., 2012, Stagakis et al., 2019). Considering the complexity of land covers and surface materials and the spatial representativeness of in-situ heat flux measurements, a combination of new techniques and modelling approaches is needed. In order to overcome the limitations derived by the spatial extent of the

measurements, satellite missions offer a unique opportunity to explore the different components of urban energy budget.

Stagakis et al. (2019) analyzed CO₂ flux in the city of Heraklion by combining land cover and morphology datasets with Eddy Covariance measurements, with the objective of establishing temporal patterns, the influence of winds and land cover classification and estimating annual CO₂ emissions. Accurate land cover maps were created considering a classification formed by 8 classes (buildings, paved surfaces, major roads, residential roads, high vegetation, low vegetation, bare soil, and water), morphology and roughness were estimated by the use of DSM and DTM products and data of a tower-based Eddy Covariance system collected for one year. The analysis gave as results the estimation of the CO₂ seasonal and diurnal patterns according to the variations of air temperature and wind direction; analysis of the CO₂ patterns according to the distribution of land cover classes; analysis of CO₂ fluxes according to weighted land cover fractions and estimation of daily and annual total CO₂ emissions.

7.2 Relevant EU projects

[CO2 Human Emissions](#) (CHE, H2020 2017 – 2020) is an initiative to explore the development of a European system to monitor human activity related carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions across the world. Such capacity is vital to support Europe's leading role in worldwide action to address climate change. The CHE project started on October 2017, bringing together a consortium of 22 European partners and lasting for over three years.

7.3 Potential benchmark for CURE

The methodologies described in the state-of-the-art section are useful as a benchmark for the development of the CURE CO₂ emission App. Results of previous research are well documented and are based on available data and modelling approaches. CURE will further advance on these methodologies by creating a product, based on individual source and sink processes modelling, at neighborhood or block scale, that will provide necessary input in decision-making processes at urban scale. Evaluation will be done through Eddy Covariance measurements.

8 APP 05 - URBAN FLOOD RISK

8.1 Description of CURE App

Flooding can cause major disruptions in cities, and lead to significant impacts on people, the economy and on the environment. These impacts may be exacerbated by climate and socio-economic changes. Resilience thinking has become an important way for city planners and decision makers to manage flood risks. Despite different definitions of resilience (Hammond et al., 2015), a consistent theme is that flood resilient cities are impacted less by extreme

flood events. Therefore, flood risk professionals and planners need to understand flood impacts to build flood resilient cities.

The flood related products developed in the context of Copernicus EMS provide information about location, intensity and optionally evolution of flood hazards. Thus, they represent key input into identification of exposed assets, population and infrastructure and assessment of flood-related risks. State-of-the-art and weather-independent radar data, with high revisit time periods enable acquisition intervals at even less than a week, facilitate monitoring of evolution of both torrential and long-term events. Hypothetic inundation extent and depth relevant for selected flood recurrent frequency (e.g., 50-yr, 100-yr) could be modelled based on accurate hydro- meteorological records, land cover maps and digital terrain model. Using current satellite imagery obtained in standard or rapid acquisition mode, the most recent information about extents and impacts of ongoing flood emergency could be provided in a matter of days.

CURE will use EMS and CLMS (see **Figure 3**) data to provide flood risk maps, combining flood hazard maps with maps of assets (land cover/land use at building block level, buildings, and infrastructure elements). Information on land cover/use, building types and population density and monetary value of built-up areas where available, will be used to quantify the vulnerability of exposed assets to floods. Using the flood intensity of detected or modelled flood hazard (which is represented usually by inundation depth) the flood risk will be estimated. Such information represents key inputs into Flood Risk Mitigation plans and evacuation scenarios at municipal or regional level. Effective adaptation strategies are needed, which combine flood protection grey infrastructure with Nature Based Solution (NBS) and risk financing schemes to manage floods and buffer their economic impacts (Schanze, 2017). Integration of Urban Flood Risk App in CURE portfolio will proceed to this direction; it will be developed in Copenhagen (front runner city) and transferred to Ostrava (follower city).

Figure 3 Baseline design of the Urban Flood Risk Service

8.2 Summary of state of the art methods

The approaches and methodologies used for assessing flood and its vulnerability evolved during the past years. Past flood studies were built based on field analysis, physical and socioeconomic approaches. After 2000 remote sensing data started playing an important role (mainly Landsat and multispectral data) in spatial vulnerability assessment. After 2010, the use of three-dimensional hydrological modelling gained importance. Recently, RADARSAT data, synthetic aperture radar (SAR), Sentinel-1 & 2 are being used to analyze flood vulnerability (Rehman et al., 2019). Therefore, the main components of the urban risk analysis (hazard, exposure and vulnerability) evolved in approaches, methodologies and datasets, thus, regarding the state of the art it has been distinguished between how Copernicus data can be used as an input for the models to determine the hazard by flooding or to generate flood mapping from satellite images. IS

The hazard analysis is mainly focused on the physical system. Nkwunonwo et al. (2020) did a review of the current status of flood modelling for urban flood risk management. The following **Figure 4** summarizes the classification scheme which is based on spatial dimensionality and mathematical complexity.

Figure 4 Classification scheme of modeling methodologies (Nkwunonwo et al., 2020)

One-dimensional flood models such as ISIS, MIKE 11, SWMM and HECRAS among others, are characterized by a limited data requirement but they also have some limitation in their representation of hydrological processes (Nkwunonwo et al., 2020).

The two-dimensional flood models such as LISFLOOD-FP, TUTFLOW, SOBEK and MIKE 21 among others have a major advantage of the comprehensive representation of flow hydrodynamics along with small scale topographic features. The use of two-dimensional flood models has been increased thanks to the advances in remote sensing technology and improved computing capacity (Ochoa-Rodríguez et al., 2013).

There is the option to follow the 1D–2D (sewer–surface) coupled method where a 1D sewer flow is connected with a 2D surface flow (e.g., Infoworks, MIKE FLOOD) (Bulti and Abebe, 2020, Zhang et al., 2016). The three-dimensional flood models solve the full Navier-Stoke equations and consider flow of flood water as completely three-dimensional (e.g. FEM model) (Zhang et al., 2016). Depending on whether the model is semi-distributed or fully-distributed, losses are estimated at each subcatchment (e.g. Sobek) or grid element (e.g. InfoWorks, MIKE, CityCat).

In the **Table 1**, a summary of the required input data for urban flood modelling is presented.

Table 1 Required data for urban flood analysis

Required information	Description	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution	Data format
Precipitation events	Precipitation for different return periods (the duration, intensity and frequency of a rain). Usually the information available is historical data from a weather station. Ideally, long ten-minute historical series, hourly or daily data are available.	For pluvial flood, shorter rainfalls are analyzed (from 30 minutes up to 3 hours) For fluvial flood (from 6 hours up to 2 or 3 days)	In case spatially distributed rainfall information is available, a GIS layer (shapefile) with the polygons is added and the corresponding rainfall file is referenced	Txt file (optional GIS layer, shapefile)
Digital terrain model (DTM)	Topographic information of the terrain.	The use of the most recent DTM is recommended as it incorporates the latest changes in the terrain and therefore better represents the actual state.	It is recommended that for a micro-scale study a resolution of 1 meter be used and for a mesoscale study a resolution of between 5 and 10 meters (depending on the extension of the study area and the computer capacity available).	Ascii or raster files

DTM for hydrology	In some cases, the buildings are included in the digital model, developing the digital terrain model for hydrology which is very useful	Same as DTM	Same as DTM	Same as DTM
Buildings	Location of the buildings to exclude the area that the buildings occupy. Therefore, the water cannot flow through that space. In case there is a green roof, this can be specified to some of the models.	It is recommended to use the most recent information	Not applicable	shapefile
Green areas	Location of the green areas. Used to later define the coefficient of friction	It is recommended to use the most recent information	Not applicable	shapefile
Soil type	Used to further define the infiltration capacity of the soil. In case there is a need for including specific pavement infiltration, then we should have information about the infiltration rate of these materials	It is recommended to use the most recent information	Not applicable	Shapefile and txt
Urban drainage network*	It refers to the information on the urban drainage network: gullies, manholes and drains.	It is recommended to use the most recent information	Not applicable	It used to have 3 files: one for each element (manholes, etc.)
Boundary conditions	The simulations are forced according to the defined boundary conditions, which represent the additional water inputs to rain in the model. External water sources can force the water level at the domain boundary to follow a certain condition (e.g. river or tidal water level).	The data with the highest resolution should be selected according to the resolution adopted for the precipitation	Not applicable	Txt file

* It is difficult to have good quality data

Other approaches, not linked with modeling, can be useful for urban flood maps generation. During the last decade considerable effort has been spent on developing algorithms for flood delineation from SAR imagery. In general, these algorithms can be divided into single-image analysis and change detection approaches (Schlaffer et al., 2015).

In the most basic single-image processing architecture, the water mapping algorithm is applied to a single S-1 image, using some ancillary data, such as a digital elevation model, and maps of land cover and historical water extent (Figure 5). Based on a comparison of flooded and non-flooded S-1 SAR images, changes of flooded areas can be detected more reliably than single-image approaches (Matgen et al., 2020). In urban areas, water detection is very challenging due to the shadowing effects from buildings as a result of the sidelooking viewing geometry of SAR satellite sensors (Bioresita et al., 2019).

Figure 5 Processing architecture for global flood monitoring using S-1 SAR image data (Matgen et al., 2020).

For the identification of flood-prone areas a preliminary delineation can be carried out by DEM-based procedures that rely on basin geomorphologic features. Such procedures may provide a preliminary delineation of the flood-prone areas useful for the planning of numerical analysis, and for insurance companies (Manfreda et al., 2011, Manfreda et al., 2014).

Finally, regarding the exposure and vulnerability analysis high spatial resolution EO data improves the knowledge regarding e.g. population, economic development, and critical infrastructure (Armenakis et al., 2017).

8.3 Relevant EU projects

The [URBIS](#) (CIS 2014 – 2017) project has focused on development of innovative methodologies, services, tools and associated business strategies ('URBIS Solutions') to support integrated solutions for the urban growth challenges related to urban (re-)development. The URBIS Solution – Flood Risk Assessment tool is based on URBIS Grey Layer and URBIS Green Layer and include following elements:

- Production of dataset - URBIS Grey Layer - of potential development areas (brownfields) in the city-region based on location of sites inside/outside flood zones;
- Production of dataset - URBIS Green and Open Space Layer – to identify non-brownfield potential development sites or green sites with potential for natural water retention within the urban envelope;
- Delivery of advanced/specific indicators – specifying characteristics of each site relevant for estimation of its risk of flood, based on its location in respect of flood zones defined in the city-region and other site characteristics;
- Support of integration of local specific datasets or knowledge – concerning local information about environmental risk zones);
- Support of interactive thematic analysis - focusing on assessment of flood risk for potential development sites in the city/region via the URBIS Integration Tool and Evaluation Tool.

[EO4SD Urban](#) was an ESA project that aimed at deriving key geo-information products from Earth Observation data in support of urban development programmes. Within a dedicated subproject on Risk Management EO4SD aimed to assist users of flood and terrain motion services with higher-level analytical products using innovative geo-statistical methods, addressing (specially for the primary products) e.g. fragmentation, connectivity and access, and environment impact.

[MUFFIN](#) (Multi-scale urban flood forecasting- from local tailored systems to a pan-european service, Water JPI) has worked to bridge the gap between the urban and large-scale hydrological modelling communities, providing mutual benefits and an arena for new thinking. The project has developed innovative systems and solutions that diminish the adverse effects of urban flooding. The basic approach was to analyze, develop, join, compare and evaluate observational and forecasting systems operating at different scales (local, regional/national, continental). During the first phase of the project, local forecasting systems were developed and optimized for selected sub-basins in these cities. In parallel, the hydrological model HYPE was developed for high-resolution modelling and set up for the same sub-basins. In the second phase of the project, coordinated forecasting experiments were carried out in order to explore the benefits and limitations of each type of model system as well as the prospect of combining them.

[INXCES](#) (Water JPI, 2016-2019). During the project period new innovative technological methods for risk assessment and mitigation of extreme hydroclimatic events has been developed and including optimization of urban water-dependent ecosystem services at the catchment level, for a spectrum of rainfall events. INXCES used and enhance innovative 3D terrain analysis and visualization technology coupled with state-of-the-art satellite remote sensing to develop cost-effective risk assessment tools for urban flooding, aquifer recharge, ground stability and subsidence. INXCES used quick scan tools that will help decision makers and other actors to improve the understanding of urban and peri-urban terrains and identify

options for cost effective implementation of water management solutions, which will reduce the negative impacts of extreme events, maximize beneficial uses of rainwater and stormwater for small to intermediate events, and provide long-term resilience in light of future climate changes.

In the project [IMPRES](#) (IMproving PRedictions and management of hydrological Extremes, H2020 2015 – 2019) forecasting systems and management procedures was analysed and improved. The requirements for daily operations and long-term planning were harmonized, providing evidence-based solutions for improved management support. The project also designed innovative risk assessment concepts for hydrological extremes that respond to the limitations of existing methods and assessment practices.

The [PEARL](#) (Preparing for Extreme And Rare events in coastal regions FP7 2014 – 2018) project addressed the threats posed in terms of flood prediction and control, by taking into account governance and socio-economic issues. The project developed novel technologies and methods for a holistic and cost-effective risk reduction framework, by linking risk and root cause assessment, event prediction, forecast and warning, development of adaptive structural and non-structural strategies and active stakeholder participation of real case studies in Europe and internationally.

8.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

The methodologies described in the state-of-the-art section are useful as a benchmark for the development of the CURE Urban Flood Risk App for the different components of urban risk analysis; this is hazard analysis through modelling or water mapping through satellite images. Results of previous research are well documented and are based on available data and modelling approaches. CURE will further advance on both approaches for the flood risk management:

- CURE data can serve as an input for physical models (such as ISIS, MIKE FLOOD and others) for example for digital elevation model and the rainfall data under climate change projections.
- Satellite images from Copernicus are the base for flooding mapping.

9 APP 06 - URBAN SUBSIDENCE, MOVEMENTS AND DEFORMATION RISK

9.1 Description of CURE App

Ground movements are responsible for hundreds of deaths and billions of Euros lost annually. Similar to floods the threat they pose is increasing due to urbanization, land use changes, but also changes in water flows under and around the city in general due to climate change and

related drought, increasingly intense rainfalls or sea level rise. For over than 20 years, Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR) has been providing ground deformation data at centimeter precision. In the past decade, new ways of processing satellite radar images have been developed using Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI) that allow round movements over wide areas to be detected and monitored with even greater sensitivity. Free and routinely-available SAR data collected by Sentinel-1 sensors' constellation within Copernicus programme represent a unique opportunity for applying these methods on operational level on a global scale (Pepe and Calò, 2017).

Recently awarded state-of-the-art service (TACR Governance Award 2018) developed by GISAT (Kolomaznik and Hlavacova, 2018) provides to responsible authorities both synoptic and detailed knowledge about localization, extent and magnitude of exposure to terrain slow motions due to subsidence or slope instability (landslide risk), and building or infrastructure deformations (due to terrain motions or maintenance failure) both in urban, rural or natural environment. The service is based on interferometric persistent scatters technique - processing of time series of high or very-high resolution satellite SAR imagery which enable detection of up to millimeter displacements – and has been demonstrated in number of national (Hlavacova et al., 2017, Lazecký et al., 2010) and global EMS related activations (Kolomaznik and Ivana, 2017).

In the framework of CURE, the cross-cutting aspects of urban subsidence will benefit from the combination of EMS, CLMS and potentially C3S services utilized for subsidence risk assessment App, coupling hazard monitoring with up-to-date assets information (land cover/land use at building block level, buildings, and grey infrastructure elements) and climate change scenarios (similar to flood risk service described above). Accurately assessing threats and identifying vulnerabilities is critical to understanding and managing the subsidence risk to the actual city assets. This cross-cutting features will be further streamlined and the entire application be integrated in CURE.

9.2 Summary of state of the art methods

Urban subsidence is commonly measured by using SAR sensors and InSAR techniques. SAR measurements have two observables: the amplitude and the phase. To quantify the deformation of land surface, InSAR methods are applied to detect changes between the interferometric signal of two acquisitions. However, the signal additionally contains noise and other confounding factors which blur the signal of interest. It is therefore necessary to accurately isolate the actual displacement from the remaining components. Therefore, the analysis of reflectors which are characterized by causing a small noise component can be focused. Of those, two different types exist: so-called distributed scatterers (DS), which have a constant response over time due to different small scattering objects (Crosetto et al., 2016) or so-called persistent (or permanent) scatterers (PS), which have a constant response over time but are caused by strong reflecting objects (Crosetto et al., 2016).

PSI focuses on such PS. By nature, objects such as buildings, electrical towers or other manmade structures provide a stable electromagnetic response through time, which makes them suitable persistent scatterers (Zhou et al., 2009, Tomás et al., 2014). Due to the high density of suitable objects for PSI in urban areas, this method is well suited for mapping urban subsidence and has already been used in several studies for this purpose (Catalao et al., 2020, Scifoni et al., 2016, Minderhoud et al., 2020). Minderhoud et al., 2020, for example use PSInSAR, a trademarked PSI algorithm, to map subsidence in the Mekong delta, Vietnam, using ground subsidence data from EMS services (EMSN057 and EMSN062).

Other methods, such as the Stanford Method for Persistent Scatterers (StaMPS) and SqueeSAR also base on the observation of persistent scatterers. While StaMPS incorporates more points as PS and is also applicable in non-urban terrain (Osmanoğlu et al., 2016), SqueeSAR considers not only persistent scatterers but also distributed scatterers (Osmanoğlu et al., 2016). Distributed scatterers extend over large areas and demonstrate a homogeneous signal response, such as fields or bare earth (Falorni et al., 2011). The small-baseline subset (SBAS) method considers only distributed scatterers (Osmanoğlu et al., 2016) and was also used in different studies to map subsidence (Solari et al., 2017, Arangio et al., 2014).

9.3 Relevant EU projects

[PANGEO](#) (FP7 project, February 2011 – January 2014) aimed to develop products integrating interpreted InSAR terrain-motion data, geological information, and land cover and land use data contained within the Urban Atlas. The integration and interpretation, plus a validation of key features observed, were made by the corresponding national geological survey for the towns concerned. The project has demonstrated the potential for the self-sustainability of services providing InSAR-derived terrain motion data.

The FP7 project [RASOR](#) aimed to develop a service that performs a multi-hazard risk analysis for the full disaster management cycle. Among others, it presents subsidence rates for selected areas in Europe, shows the impact on several factors, such as environment or economy, and presents the exposure to, among others, buildings, road and railway networks and population. The project ran from December 2013 to May 2016. The platform can be accessed online, see: <http://www.rasor-project.eu/>

The FP7 project [RETURN](#), running from January 2013 to December 2016, focused on the prediction of building damage due to tunnel-induced subsidence on city-scale (Clarke and Laefer, 2014).

[SUBCOAST](#) was a FP7 project starting April 2010 and ending September 2013. Its aim was to develop a service which monitors land subsidence in selected coastal areas in Europe. It also

includes the assessment of consecutive risks, such as flood risks, and evaluates the impact of subsidence due to man-made and natural causes. The platform cannot be accessed online anymore.

Besides, above methods are successfully used in numerous ESA projects in sustainable development and resilience context (e.g. <https://eo4sd.esa.int/>) and operationally applied in number of Copernicus EMS activations. In addition, European Ground Motion Service is currently under preparation within CLMS portfolio. For more information see: <https://land.copernicus.eu/user-corner/technical-library/egms-white-paper>

9.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

Satellite radar interferometry is widely considered as one of the most robust and reliable techniques for ground motion monitoring at local scale and over wide areas. All presented methods have so far been used to measure land subsidence in urban areas. (Solari et al., 2018) stresses the advantage of point-like data, which is capable of not only mapping subsidence over large areas but also presenting the displacement of single buildings. In the recent years, satellite radar interferometry has undergone a rapid evolution thanks to the launch of the Sentinel-1 constellation, to the refinement of algorithms, and to the increased computational capability offered by cloud computing platforms. Nowadays, radar data is freely available streaming from Copernicus programme (e.g. Sentinel-1 from 2014). In addition, suitable radar data reaches back to 1992, which enables historical processing over almost three decades. There is the high demand for interferometric products as wide area mapping or monitoring tools which are a direct request from national, regional or city entities and administrations involved in e.g. geohazard risk management or infrastructures monitoring.

10 APP 07 - URBAN AIR QUALITY

10.1 Description of CURE App

Urban air quality is a multi-scale problem. Nitrogen dioxide concentrations at street-level scale are influenced by regional (rural) background concentrations, urban increments due to local industrial and traffic sources, and an additional contribution due to the recirculation in the street canyon. CURE proposes a solution which captures the multi-scale aspect by combining several models into an integrated model chain, the ATMO-Street chain (Lefebvre et al., 2013). The final outputs of this service are street-level (5 m x 5 m resolution) yearly mean NO₂ maps Summary of state of the art methods.

The core of the methodology consists of a traffic emission model, FASTRACE, and a Gaussian dispersion model coupled to a street-canyon module, IFDM-OSPM (Lefebvre et al., 2013). The model chain has been validated using several measurement campaigns, focusing on spatial patterns and time series alike (Lefebvre et al., 2013, Lefebvre et al., 2011, Lefebvre and Vranckx, 2013).

10.2 Summary of state of the art methods

For the assessment of air quality, simulation of four major processes is required: emission of pollutants, transport / dispersion of pollutants (dependent on transport of meteorological variables), physico-chemical conversion and deposition (Kadaverugu et al., 2019). The interactions within these processes that need to be simulated depend on the spatial scale of the modelling. For the European to global scale, CAMS (<https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu>) provides daily forecasts and analysis bases on satellite data. However, with grid cells of 10 km² this is too coarse for the CURE goals. For local assessment of air quality, typically street canyons are studied with a variety of air quality models. CAMS can often be used to provide the background pollution to these detailed models, who then at street level address the above mentioned processes, by taking local polluters (from cars, industry) and street geometries into account.

Lefebvre et al. (2013) separate air quality models into box models, Gaussian plume models, CFD dispersion models or combined approaches.

Box models, such as OSPM (Berkowicz et al., 2008) parameterize the effect of street canyons at the local scale. As these models require very detailed input data, their application is often limited to one or few streets. On the other hand, Gaussian plume models, such as AERMOD, can easily take into account a complete city area. However, they lack the street canyon effect in their simulations, which can be significant for busy roads confined by continuous building-walls (Lefebvre et al., 2013).

An alternate approach is to apply CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) – based dispersion models, such as ENVI-Met (Bruse and Fleer, 1998), WA CFD-RANS (Santiago et al., 2017) or PALM (Maronga et al., 2020). These models explicitly resolve the 3D geometry of the city and enable one to directly compute the dispersion in the street-canyon flow. However, because their computational expensive nature, they are currently still of limited use for large areas or large simulation times.

Combinations between Gaussian models and box models, such as UBM-OSPM (Berkowicz et al., 2008) and ADMS-urban (Righi et al., 2009), have already been applied to some cities. Although coupling these models combines the advantages of both approaches, it also increases difficulties in other areas such as being consistent or assimilating the known measurements in the city (Lefebvre et al., 2013).

10.3 Relevant EU projects

Within the [VEG-AIR](#) research project (FP7 2012 – 2014) different implications of urban vegetation on the micrometeorology and microclimatology of cities were investigated. The research was focused on two aspects, namely (i) on the effects of avenue-trees on natural ventilation and pollutant dispersion, and (ii) on the effects of various vegetative measures (avenue-trees, facade greening, roof greening) on air temperatures in the built environment. For the assessment of the effect of vegetation on pollutant dispersion, a CFD model was employed. Area of research was the city of Arnhem, the Netherlands. However, the results have not been published online.

[ATMOSYS](#) (EC Life+ 2010 – 2013) developed a generic web-based service, containing novel elements specifically designed to evaluate and analyze air pollution in European hot spot regions. The system is established for the hotspot region Flanders in the North of Belgium but can be deployed in other regions as well. The established system is based on advanced technology, including prognostic 3-D atmospheric computer models (AURORA, RIO-IDFM), results from recent and on-going air pollution measurement campaigns in urban agglomerations and generic OGC-communication protocols to facilitate a fully automated web-based service. The project website still provides daily air quality forecasts as well as yearly air quality maps for Belgium.

The [PASODOBLE](#) (FP7 2010 – 2013) project was carried out in the context of the European Earth Observation Programme Copernicus (previously known as GMES). Its overarching goal was to integrate observations and develop localized information — a goal it accomplished for at least 30 regions and cities across Europe. Tools were developed. Through close collaboration with the Copernicus Atmosphere Service (MACC), PASODOBLE has linked global satellite and modelling capacities to local needs and applications. Focusing on hot spots, the service portfolio is complementary to the Copernicus Atmosphere Service. A range of tools and methodologies have been developed and improved, among them AURORA (Kumar et al., 2012), a regional scale air quality model.

[ACTRIS](#) (H2020, multiple projects, ongoing) is a European Research Infrastructure (RI) which provides access to its facilities, open-access data, research support, instrument calibration and development, and training to various user groups.

10.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

Most EU air quality products are regional scale or coarser (CAMS). Local air quality services are typically also local in areal coverage and therefore for most CURE cities not available for comparison.

11 APP 08 - URBAN THERMAL COMFORT

11.1 Description of CURE App

Human activities and human health are heavily impacted by thermal stress. Urban areas exhibit an important increase in thermal discomfort compared to rural regions both during the night (UHI) as during the day due to increased radiative exposure, lower wind speeds and higher air temperatures. In particular, sensitive population groups such as children, elderly and sick persons are more heavily impacted. During extreme heat waves, there is an uneven amplification of thermal discomfort inside the cities that leads to even higher impacts, increasing human mortality. Moreover, global climate projections consistently point towards an increase of the number, duration, and intensity of heat waves (Meehl and Tebaldi, 2004, Diffenbaugh and Giorgi, 2012). Recent work by VITO has shown that climate change may lead to a tenfold increase in the expected number of heat wave days within cities by the end of the century (Lauwaet et al., 2015). The CURE thermal comfort App will build upon the urban climate model UrbClim (De Ridder et al., 2015), developed at VITO, providing urban air temperature, humidity and wind speed at 100 m x 100 m spatial resolution. The thermal comfort App will provide thermal comfort indicators such as e.g., the wet-bulb globe temperature, aggregating different climatic stressors for the entire urban area. These thermal comfort indicators are much more linked to human health impacts compared to indicators solely based on air temperatures.

11.2 Summary of state of the art methods

For the characterisation of heat stress and thermal comfort, the wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT) is selected as this is the ISO standard to quantify human thermal comfort (ISO, 1989). The (outdoor) WBGT is the weighted sum of the natural wet bulb temperature T_w , the black globe temperature T_g , and the dry bulb (ambient) temperature T_a :

$$WBGT = 0.7T_w + 0.2T_g + 0.1T_a$$

Lemke and Kjellstrom (2012) review different measurement methods of WBGT using meteorological instruments. Lauwaet et al. (2020) show how WBGT can also be derived using modelled values of hourly 2 m air temperatures, specific humidity, and wind speeds. Downward solar radiation and surface pressure are also needed, and were taken from the ERA-interim re-analysis of the European Centre for medium-range weather forecasting (ECMWF). Additionally, building height and tree height are needed to calculate the amount of shade. Using this fine scale modelling approach, WBGT at 100 m grid cells can be calculated for larger areas, e.g. covering complete cities.

Other approaches in literature to determine WBGT focus either on much larger scale with lower spatial resolutions, or on local measurements. Willett and Sherwood (2012) implemented a simplified WBGT which uses only temperature and humidity. This allows for

using large global data bases with temperature measurements and therefore deriving coarse global maps of simplified WVTG.

There is special equipment available for direct field measurements of WBGT. Nikolopoulou and Lykoudis (2006) carried out measurements in 7 European cities, in Greece, Switzerland, Germany and UK. Additional interviews illustrate the differences in adaptation between the cities.

Although WBGT is an ISO standard and frequently used, many scientific publications use Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET) as thermal index, which is defined a standard by the German VDI guidelines. Also Universal thermal climate index (UTCI), Perceived Temperature (PT) and Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) are used. Especially PET, PMV and UTCI are frequently implemented in CFD models (e.g. in ENVI-met or PALM-4U) and therefore relatively easy to derive for high resolution model areas, however with limited spatial extension because of computational costs.

11.3 Relevant EU projects

[RAMSES](#) (Reconciling Adaptation, Mitigation and Sustainable dEvelopment for citieS, FP7 2012 – 2017) was a five-year project focusing on climate change adaptation planning, including the calculation of climate change-related damage and adaptation costs. Among other achievements, the project developed and applied tools to assess climate impacts, vulnerability, and risks in cities that evaluate climate impacts on priority sectors, and provide a rational basis for testing the effectiveness of adaptation strategies.

The objective of the Pan-European Urban Climate Service (PUCS, meanwhile renamed to [Climate-fit.City](#), H2020 2017 – 2020) project is to establish a service that translates the best available scientific urban climate data into relevant information for public and private end-users operating in cities. To this purpose, multiple services have been developed, among others a heat and health service using VITOs UrbCLIM model for thermal comfort modelling.

Rediscovering the urban realm and open spaces ([RUROS](#), FP5 2001 – 2005): The objective of this project was to map thermal comfort conditions in open spaces based on field surveys and data. Of key concern was that the methodology be easy to use and understand and tailored for planners and architects. Analyzing the spatial distribution of meteorological parameters and comfort indices was the initial step in thermal mapping. Important aspects of consideration included site morphology, meteorological and time parameters. Morphology comprised building measurements, surface types and vegetation. Solar/thermal radiation and wind speed were the focus of the meteorological parameters. By taking influencing factors and variables into consideration for the design and use of open space, both risk and suitability can be carefully evaluated.

11.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

Urban thermal comfort expressed by WBGT can be either measured or modelled. In prevailing EU projects such as Climate-fit.City and RAMSES, experience has been gained on the use of models (such as UrbClim) for simulation of thermal comfort using this indicator. Especially the knowledge on the establishment of a service in this respect might be useful for CURE.

12 APP 09 - URBAN HEAT STORAGE MONITORING

12.1 Description of CURE App

Among all the effects caused by the substitution of natural ecosystems by urban land-use, the most pronounced, concerning the urban energy balance, is the increase in the amount of the change of energy stored in the urban canopy, i.e. the storage heat flux (ΔQS), which is approximately 2 - 6 times larger than in non-urban canopies. ΔQS is the net flow change of heat stored in urban canopy and represents all the mechanisms of storage of energy within the volume, i.e., in the air, on trees in vegetation, in buildings, constructed in their the ground, etc. (Offerle et al., 2005). The Objective Hysteresis Model (OHM) (Grimmond et al., 1991) is a well-established and robust method using net radiation Q^* and a set of Land Use/Land Cover dependent coefficients for the calculation of ΔQS . An updated version of the Objective Hysteresis Model (OHM) that has been recently released (Lindberg et al., 2018) will be used in CURE to estimate heat storage at local scale. The method will be adapted to Copernicus Core Services.

12.2 Summary of state of the art method

Roberts et al. (2006) identified four different methods for estimating heat storage: the energy balance residual method (RES), parameterization, numerical modelling and use of thermal mass scheme (TMS). RES is a straight forward approach, by determining all other terms of the energy balance. Parameterization takes the surface types into account and requires coefficients describing the relation of heat storage to energy flux for each surface type. An example of numerical modelling of the urban heat storage is the Town Energy Balance (TEB) (Masson, 2000). The TEB scheme performs surface-atmosphere coupling and its primary aim is to parameterize surface-atmosphere turbulent fluxes into the lowest level of mesoscale atmospheric models, that is, through the top of the Urban Canopy Layer (UCL). The Thermal Mass Scheme (TMS) estimates urban ΔQ_s using basic concepts of heat conduction and volumetric heat storage in a material (Roberts et al., 2006).

Parameterization is the favored approach when using remote sensing, although these studies are sparse (Lindberg et al., 2020). The objective hysteresis model (OHM) (Grimmond et al., 1991) is often used. Sun et al. (2017) adapted this approach to an OHM for better estimation

of the coefficients and implementation in land surface models. Another example is Complete Aspect Ratio (CAR) (Rigo and Parlow, 2007). Element Surface Temperature Method (ESTM) (Offerle et al., 2005) reduces the 3-dimensional urban volume to four 1-dimensional elements (i.e. building roofs, walls, internal mass and ground (road, vegetation, etc.)). Lindberg et al. (2020) note, that when using remote sensing, often anthropogenic and storage heat flux terms are not separated (e.g. in (Rigo and Parlow, 2007, Kato and Yamaguchi, 2007)).

12.3 Relevant EU projects

In the project [URBANFLUXES](#) (H2020 2015-2019) a methodology estimating all terms for the urban energy balance (UEB) has been developed. Because of the accompanying measurement network, the developed methodologies could be validated. For ΔQ_S the ESTM method was applied and results were evaluated considering the complete UEB including the anthropogenic heat flux.

12.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

Cross-comparisons with the respective URBANFLUXES products (Chrysoulakis et al., 2018) could be carried out. These are based on the more detailed Element Surface Temperature Method (Offerle et al., 2005).

13 APP 10 - NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS

13.1 Description of CURE App

Nature-Based solutions are gaining relevance for the enhancement of urban sustainability and resilience, given the increased evidence about a wide range of socioeconomic, environmental and climate related co-benefits which they provide. Specifically, green roofs could improve performance of single buildings (e.g. energy consumption) as well as generate at the same time important positive effects in public spaces at city scale, like water run-off regulation and flood prevention or contribution to urban heat island moderation and air quality improvement. Strategic planning and zoning approaches are essential in the decision-making process and thus the integration of NBS into sectorial procedures. This App will allow urban planners to identify areas with highest potential of roof retrofitting and quantify maximum potential deployment of green roofs by assessing at city scale key enabling conditions for installation (i.e. roof size and slope, orientation, use, shadowing and other building suitability factors), providing decision makers with alternative scenarios on green roof potential. Alongside, in combination with other CURE Apps, benefits related to key resilience challenges as flooding, heat stress or air quality will be modelled and evaluated.

Both outputs will inform local decision making by benchmarking alternative scenarios of green roofs potential.

13.2 Summary of state of the art methods

The recent awareness of cities to actively act against climate change and environmental issues, as well as the spread of NBS, lead to a crescent demand on effective planning tools for decision-making. Different methodologies have been developed to incorporate climate change adaptation solutions in urban regeneration processes and urban planning, considering identification, mapping as well as effectiveness evaluation. These approaches have resulted in the adoption and publication of guidelines by Local Governments (Epelde et al., 2018, Udalsarea, 2017). Despite the increasing amount of available data and the numerous possibilities their analysis gives, practical applications and low efforts methods need to be addressed. To deal with different data sources, type and scales, data models, able to structure heterogeneous information, are becoming a common tool for planning purposes. 3D city models have been used as valuable tools to bring together semantic and geometric data. They have been used for several purposes, such as the calculation of solar maps in CityGML format, based on LiDAR and other parameters, which estimates the annual solar radiation per square meter, considering the roof surfaces of buildings, the orography, the urban shape and shadings between constructions or natural elements (Prieto, 2017).

In recent years, satellite imagery has been identified as an opportunity for monitoring urban environments, including NBS detection, implementation scenarios, effectiveness and monitoring. Wellmann et al. (2020) have investigated the correlation between population and vegetation density changes, in the city of Berlin, considering the period comprised between 1988 and 2018. A regression-based spectral unmixing method was applied to Landsat satellite imagery, in order to derive a long time series of fractional vegetation cover, taking advantages of using all the bands of the image, instead of the two commonly used for the NDVI. The method is purely quantitative and qualitative information on the type, quality and connectivity, which are important factors for planning and performance assessment, is missing. NDVI and land surface temperature, were used as main parameters by Herrera-Gomez et al. (2017) to estimate the additional surface of green roofs needed to mitigate the effects of urban heat island and the increase of temperature due to climate change in Seville. Values were obtained by the use of Sentinel 2 and Landsat 7 ETM and compared between them, demonstrating an inverse relationship between land surface temperature and NDVI. Results show that less vegetated surface is needed when using Landsat images, varying according to different SERES A2 climatic scenarios and global models analyzed. The (negative) correlation among Land Surface Temperature and NDVI have also been demonstrated in the city of Milan by Colaninno and Morello (2019) through the use of Geographically Weighted Regression models. Current and potential green roof mapping has been developed by Marconcini and Metz (2016b) as part of the DECUMANUS project, with the aim of identifying existing green roof and estimating the potential of transforming roofs into green roofs. The

process has been developed by using very high-resolution satellite/airborne color infrared (CIR) remote sensing data and height information. In the CURE project this method will be compared with the [algorithm](#) developed by Tecnia which, based on the real slope of the roof and the classification of the albedo through LIDAR information, allows the automation of the cataloging processes. Methodologies often identify roofs which meet greening requirements but lack of suitability prioritization. A comprehensive study on the suitability evaluation criteria of large-scale roof greening, which consider buildings, the environment, and social and demographic aspects on Xiamen Island has been addressed by Xu et al. (2020). Remote sensing images and deep learning are used to extract roof patches of buildings, while TOPSIS method is used for multi-criteria decision-making analysis. TerraMAP, a high-resolution satellite imagery analysis tool, based on Sentinel 2 HR images, has been used in Nature4cities project to create land cover maps and calculate some indicators. It allows generating data about the urban environment, in form of maps with a characterization of the land pattern (land cover, vegetation, soil patterns, buildings etc.). The tool operates in a GIS-based environment allowing the processing of information compatible with GIS software. Oswald et al. (2020) analyzed the potential and effectiveness of individual and combined climate adaptation measures, mainly enhanced albedo of sealed areas and highly evaporating green surfaces, in the city of Klagenfurt. For this purpose, a combination of data sources was used, from microscale urban climate model, climate indices, the Urban Atlas, imperviousness layer and forest cover provided by the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, in combination with a digital surface model and national and local data sets with higher resolutions.

13.3 Relevant EU projects

[Nature4cities](#) (H2020 2016 – 2021) is creating a comprehensive reference Platform for NBS, offering technical solutions, methods and tools to empower urban planning decision making. The project has developed several knowledge repositories and tools for the planning, assessment and implementation process of NBS projects, such as for example: **NBenefit\$**, for the decision making based on socio-economic assessment of NBS projects, **GREENPASS¹**, for the evaluation and assessment of the impact of green infrastructures in urban areas or **COLOUREE¹**, for giving insights for NBS best implementation area. The tools have been tested on N4C pilots and it has been necessary to collect data, including satellite images and process them to get relevant information and maps to assess these pilots or calculate different indicators. In this context, the tool **TerraMAP** established the contribution of satellite imagery to the calculation of NBS related indicators.

The overall objective of [SHELTER](#) (H2020 2019 – 2023) is to establish a data-driven and community based operational knowledge framework for heritage-led resilience enhancement and sustainable reconstruction of Historic Areas to cope with Climate Change and natural

¹ Colouree and GreenPass are already existing tools which have been further developed within the N4C project activities

hazards. The project is currently developing a methodology to collect and analyze data in a structured way, establishing criteria to identify the quality of datasets and sources in terms of interoperability and replicability standards compliancy and a roadmap to achieve the maximum and durable data exploitation. In this context, Sentinel data as well as Copernicus services products will be used. As part of the project, a multiscale and multisource data model to structure local knowledge and data of different sources will be designed. The project is still in an incipient phase, thus results will be closely monitored and synergies with NBS CURE App will be seek. The data model will store geospatial and semantic data based on international standards such as CityGML and INSPIRE. Main satellite data from Copernicus that will be considered are the Sentinel 1 (surface soil moisture and SAR GRD images) and the Sentinel 2 (true colour and NDVI). Main data services from Copernicus are the CLMS (CLC 2018, Corine Land Cover Change 2012 – 2018 and EU-DEM v1.1), the C3S (ERA5 daily average temperature of air at 2m above surface, ERA5 daily maximum temperature of air at 2m above the surface, UERRA regional reanalysis for Europe on single levels and ERA5-Land), the CAMS (Daily air quality analyses and forecasts for Europe) and the CEMS (Risk and Recovery Mapping and the Rapid Mapping).

[DECUMANUS](#) (FP7 2013 – 2016) aimed at supporting sustainable cities management by developing a set of services incorporating EO-based geo-spatial products and geo-information services to environmental and climate change strategies. The project has developed services for the following categories: 1) Urban Climate Atlas service assessing urban climate change impacts; 2) Land monitoring service providing land consumption information and urban ecosystems assessment tools; 3) City Energy Efficiency assessing energy consumption and improve energy efficiency in cities; 4) Citizen Health tools to alert the population to health risks arising from poor air quality and excessive temperatures in the urban area; 5) Population impact assessment analyzing the impact of climate change scenarios to the population. Among the results of the project, particular attention is given to the Current and Potential Green Roof Mapping.

The main objective of [Thinknature](#) (H2020 2016 – 2019) was to develop a multi-stakeholder communication platform supporting the understanding and promotion of Nature based Solutions. The project has delivered a handbook which gathers state of the art knowledge, including emerging trends in the field of monitoring and quantification of the multi-scale NBS impacts through the use of EO and Copernicus services. In the report it is highlighted the importance of having long term monitoring as well as quantitative information across spatial scales. During the project, the need to dispose of harmonized and standardized data across different countries and to monitor the effectiveness and performance of NBS against well-defined baseline emerged. EO data can therefore support this need by providing information in the short and long term, capturing changes in the environment.

13.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

According to the literature review, one of the advantages offered by the use of satellite imagery in Nature Based Solutions related studies, is the opportunity to perform the diagnosis of vegetation changes and monitoring of the sealing and de-sealing processes over time. Furthermore, the recurrence of data is compatible with decision-making processes and continuous long-term monitoring is ensured, allowing generating comparable and long track results. Recent advances in EO data and technologies are resulting in the emerging of new services and their support in NBS monitoring schemes is projected to increase exponentially (Somarakis and Stratigea, 2019). Furthermore, new algorithms, able to run almost with no operators, will allow to significantly reduce costs and time with respect to current approaches.

14 APP 11 - HEALTH IMPACTS (SOCIOECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE)

14.1 Description of CURE App

The central part of the Health Impacts application will revolve around the state-of-the-art EVA (Economic Evaluation of Air Pollution) model that has been developed by the University of Aarhus. The model consists of an impact-pathway chain based on the emissions, transport and chemical transformation of air pollutants and the population exposure and augments this data with exposure-response functions and economic valuations, to finally provide information on the health impacts and external costs caused by air pollution (Jensen et al., 2018). The quality and coverage of Real World Evidence (RWE) from the national registers offers ample opportunity to investigate the health impacts. Via the national registers, it is possible to follow a person from cradle to grave and thereby to have complete coverage of a person's health related activities. The EVA model has been validated against RWE from Danish national registers and from international cohort studies.

The added value of project CURE will be to adopt the EVA model into its application setting, upon agreement from University of Aarhus, since the model is not freely available. However, the extensive research of Aarhus University and expertise in the past 20 years and their continuous update of the EVA model would be a truly great opportunity for the CURE project and it's users to have access to.

App 11 will further investigate the link between mental health and air pollution exposure and the subsequent associated costs through available scientific literature.

The proposed App in the framework of CURE, will map health in different geographical areas, determined by e.g., differences in air quality (based on the Urban Air Quality App (Section 10) with inputs from CLMS, CAMS and C3S), thermal and surface heat assessments (based on the Surface Urban Heat Island Assessment App (section 5) and Urban Thermal Comfort App, section 11), access to green areas (e.g., by means of the methodology based on spatial

network analysis of urban green areas developed in DECUMANUS by (Marconcini and Metz, 2016a), with the outlines of the green areas being extracted from the CLMS Urban Atlas) and by researching the opportunities of heat reduction and CO₂ storage of urban trees (Copenhagen Municipality: 100.000 new trees towards 2025) and lastly socioeconomic characteristics. By comparing areas with different prerequisites, we will be able to analyze the effect of these conditions on human health.

14.2 Summary of state of the art methods

Several studies exist that evaluate the influence of environmental factors on public health. However, many of them address particular influences, such as air pollution (Ellermann et al., 2020, Anenberg et al., 2016, Im et al., 2018, Khan et al., 2019, Lelieveld et al., 2019, Brandt et al., 2013, Héroux et al., 2015, Im et al., 2019, World Health Organization, 2013), urban heat (Santamouris, 2020, Heaviside et al., 2017, Mueller et al., 2017), noise (Mueller et al., 2017) or socio-economic aspects (World Health Organization, 2009c, World Health Organization, 2009a) and focus on city to country-level. Also, studies present the resulting health impacts in different metrics, e.g. mortality, economic costs or DALY (disability-adjusted life-year).

Air pollution is an environmental factor that is often evaluated in terms of its effect on public health. The Department of Environmental Science at Aarhus University, Denmark, for example, developed several models which focus on quantifying urban and regional background pollution and air pollution on street level, integrating, among others, local measurements, meteorological data and traffic information (Ellermann et al., 2020). These models have been integrated to a web-based application which presents air pollution up to street level on an hourly basis (Khan et al., 2019). Also, the EVA-model, which builds on information on air pollution, has been developed in this department (Jensen et al., 2018). For CURE, these models can serve as a valuable reference for a complete workflow, starting with air measurements and resulting in actual economical costs.

A large scale study covering several risk factors is conducted by the WHO. Since 1990, the WHO associates external factors, such as water conditions or socio-economic aspects, to population's mortality or life expectancy (World Health Organization, 2009c). Data is updated on a yearly basis and reports are published regularly. This extensive study is the basis for several follow up studies, which focus on particular correlations between external factors and their impacts presented in the WHO report (World Health Organization, 2019, Feigin et al., 2016, James et al., 2018).

Further studies that are presented are more focused on particular aspects, such as the risk factor, the calculation of costs or the area and can serve CURE in these particular points. (Santamouris, 2020), for example, gives an extensive overview on studies that assess public health and economic costs focusing on urban heat. (Sortsø et al., 2015) provides detailed descriptions on how to calculate expected costs according to the performed service (e.g.

costs of living in nursing home, service delivered in hospitals, etc.). The study conducted by (Mueller et al., 2017) concentrates on the area of Barcelona, Spain, and presents a complete workflow to estimate health impacts (namely mortality and economic costs) due to five external factors (i.e. physical activity, air pollution, noise, heat, access to green space).

14.3 Relevant EU projects

The [DECUMANUS](#) (Development of Environment and Climate Change Urban Monitoring and Adaptation Tools for Urban Services) project objective was the provision of five sustainable decision support services to the city managers that allow the deployment of geo-spatial products in the development and implementation of climate change strategies. In particular, one service has been specifically dedicated to develop variables and indicators for identifying air pollution hotspots over the cities and their impact on different health indicators such as the mortality rates or changes in respiratory hospital admissions. This information assists users to understand the health impact of the global climate change for the local urban environment and how human health may be affected by changes caused by global warming emissions. Specifically, the two IPCC RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios have been considered. The FP7 project ran from 2013 to 2016.

[EuroHEAT](#) quantified the health effects of heat in European cities and identified options for improving the preparedness for and response to the effect of heat-waves. It ran from 2005 to 2007 and was coordinated by the WHO Europe and co-funded by the European Commission Directorate-General for Health and Consumers (World Health Organization, 2009b).

[iSCAPE](#) was a H2020 project starting in September 2016 and ending in August 2019. It aimed to control air quality in urban areas by using “passive control systems”, such as remediation strategies or behavioural change initiatives and thus to support policy makers creating more sustainable and resilient cities.

[EO2HEAVEN](#) used earth observation data to observe environmental changes (with emphasis on atmospheric, river, lake and coastal marine pollution) and evaluated their impact on human health. The FP7 project ran from February 2010 to May 2013.

14.4 Potential benchmark for CURE

The studies serve as interesting references and give an overview on how workflows can be composed, that assess the impact of environmental factors on health and economic costs. Depending on the focused environmental factor, different sources for input data can be considered; local monitoring stations, for example, can be used to measure air quality while remote sensing data can, among many others, provide information on land use and land cover or street networks and can thus serve as a source for estimating the distance to public green areas or bicycle paths. The presented studies show, how different data sources are

incorporated to estimate socio-impacts but also give examples on how to actually calculate the resulting impact, for example in economic costs.

15 REFERENCES

- ANENBERG, S. C., BELOVA, A., BRANDT, J., FANN, N., GRECO, S., GUTTIKUNDA, S., HEROUX, M. E., HURLEY, F., KRZYZANOWSKI, M. & MEDINA, S. 2016. Survey of ambient air pollution health risk assessment tools. *Risk Analysis*, 36, 1718-1736.
- ARANGIO, S., CALÒ, F., DI MAURO, M., BONANO, M., MARSELLA, M. & MANUNTA, M. 2014. An application of the SBAS-DInSAR technique for the assessment of structural damage in the city of Rome. *Structure Infrastructure Engineering*, 10, 1469-1483.
- ARMENAKIS, C., DU, E., NATESAN, S., PERSAD, R. & ZHANG, Y. 2017. Flood Risk Assessment in Urban Areas Based on Spatial Analytics and Social Factors. *Geosciences*, 7, 123.
- BERKOWICZ, R., KETZEL, M., JENSEN, S. S., HVIDBERG, M. & RAASCHOU-NIELSEN, O. 2008. Evaluation and application of OSPM for traffic pollution assessment for a large number of street locations. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 23, 296-303.
- BIORESITA, F., PUISSANT, A., STUMPF, A. & MALET, J.-P. 2019. Fusion of Sentinel -1 and Sentinel -2 image time series for permanent and temporary surface water mapping. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 40, 9026--9049.
- BOLLE, A., DEMUYNCK, A., BOUTELIGIER, R., BOSCH, S., VERWEY, A. & BERLAMONT, J. 2006. Hydraulic Modelling of the Two-directional Interaction between Sewer and River Systems. In: DELECTIC, A. & FLETCHER, T. (eds.) *7th International Conference on Urban Drainage Modelling and the 4th International Conference on Water Sensitive Urban Design*. Clayton, Vic.: Monash University.
- BRANDT, J., SILVER, J. D., CHRISTENSEN, J. H., ANDERSEN, M. S., BØNLØKKE, J. H., SIGSGAARD, T., GEELS, C., GROSS, A., HANSEN, A. B. & HANSEN, K. M. 2013. Contribution from the ten major emission sectors in Europe and Denmark to the health-cost externalities of air pollution using the EVA model system--an integrated modelling approach. *Atmospheric Chemistry Physics*, 13.
- BRUSE, M. & FLEER, H. 1998. Simulating surface-plant-air interactions inside urban environments with a three dimensional numerical model. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 13, 373-384.
- BULTI, D. T. & ABEBE, B. G. 2020. A review of flood modeling methods for urban pluvial flood application. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 6, 1293--1302.
- CATALAO, J., RAJU, D. & NICO, G. 2020. InSAR maps of land subsidence and sea level scenarios to quantify the flood inundation risk in coastal cities: The case of Singapore. *Remote Sensing*, 12, 296.
- CHENG, T., XU, Z., HONG, S. & SONG, S. 2017. Flood Risk Zoning by Using 2D Hydrodynamic Modeling : A Case Study in Jinan City. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2017, 1-8.
- CHRISTEN, A., COOPS, N. C., CRAWFORD, B. R., KELLETT, R., LISS, K. N., OLCHOVSKI, I. & TOOKE, T. R. A. 2011. Validation of modeled carbon-dioxide emissions from an urban

- neighborhood with direct eddy-covariance measurements. *Atmospheric Environment*, 45, 6057--6069.
- CHRYSOULAKIS, N., GRIMMOND, S., FEIGENWINTER, C., LINDBERG, F., GASTELLU-ETCHEGORRY, J. P., MARCONCINI, M., MITRAKA, Z., STAGAKIS, S., CRAWFORD, B., OLOFSON, F., LANDIERS, L., MORRISON, W. & PARLOW, E. 2018. Urban energy exchanges monitoring from space. *Scientific Reports*, 8.
- CLARKE, J. A. & LAEFER, D. F. 2014. Evaluation of risk assessment procedures for buildings adjacent to tunnelling works. *Tunnelling Underground Space Technology*, 40, 333-342.
- COLANINNO, N. & MORELLO, E. 2019. Modelling the impact of green solutions upon the urban heat island phenomenon by means of satellite data. 1343.
- CRAWFORD, B. & CHRISTEN, A. 2014. Spatial source attribution of measured urban eddy covariance CO₂ fluxes. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 119, 733--755.
- CRAWFORD, B., GRIMMOND, S. B., GABEY, A., MARCONCINI, M., WARD, H. C. & KENT, C. W. 2018. Variability of urban surface temperatures and implications for aerodynamic energy exchange in unstable conditions. 144, 1719-1741.
- CROSETTO, M., MONSERRAT, O., CUEVAS-GONZÁLEZ, M., DEVANTHÉRY, N. & CRIPPA, B. 2016. Persistent scatterer interferometry: A review. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry Remote Sensing*, 115, 78-89.
- DE RIDDER, K., LAUWAET, D. & MAIHEU, B. 2015. UrbClim – A fast urban boundary layer climate model. *Urban Climate*, 12, 21-48.
- DELGADO BLASCO, J. M., FOUMELIS, M., STEWART, C. & HOOPER, A. 2019. Measuring Urban Subsidence in the Rome Metropolitan Area (Italy) with Sentinel-1 SNAP-StaMPS Persistent Scatterer Interferometry. 11, 129.
- DIFFENBAUGH, N. S. & GIORGI, F. 2012. Climate change hotspots in the CMIP5 global climate model ensemble. *Climatic Change*, 114, 813-822.
- ELLERMANN, T., NYGAARD, J., NØJGAARD, J. K., NORDSTRØM, C., BRANDT, J., CHRISTENSEN, J., KETZEL, M., MASSLING, A., BOSSI, R., FROHN, L. M., GEELS, C. & JENSEN, S. S. 2020. The Danish Air Quality Monitoring Programme. Annual Summary for 2018. Scientific Report from DCE – Danish Centre for Environment and Energy No. 218.: Aarhus University, DCE – Danish Centre for Environment and Energy.
- EPELDE, L., MENDIZABAL, M., ARTETXE, A., FERNANDEZ, P., GUTIRREZ, L., GARCA-BLANCO, G. & FELIU, E. 2018. *Guía para la evaluación de la efectividad y el diseño de Soluciones Naturales como medidas de mitigación y adaptación al cambio climático*, Fundación Biodiversida. Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica.
- FALORNI, G., MORGAN, J. & ENEVA, M. 2011. Advanced InSAR techniques for geothermal exploration and production. *GRC Transactions*, 35, 1661-1666.
- FEIGENWINTER, C., VOGT, R., PARLOW, E., LINDBERG, F., MARCONCINI, M., FRATE, F. D. & CHRYSOULAKIS, N. 2018. Spatial Distribution of Sensible and Latent Heat Flux in the City of Basel (Switzerland). *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 11, 2717-2723.
- FEIGIN, V. L., ROTH, G. A., NAGHAVI, M., PARMAR, P., KRISHNAMURTHI, R., CHUGH, S., MENSAH, G. A., NORRVING, B., SHIUE, I. & NG, M. 2016. Global burden of stroke and

- risk factors in 188 countries, during 1990–2013: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013. *The Lancet Neurology*, 15, 913-924.
- FOKEN, T. 2006. 50 Years of the Monin–Obukhov Similarity Theory. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 119, 431-447.
- GARCÍA-DIÉZ, M., LAUWAET, D., HOOYBERGHS, H. & BALLESTER, J. A. 2016. Advantages of using a fast urban boundary layer model as compared to a full mesoscale model to simulate the urban heat island of Barcelona. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9, 4439--4450.
- GFDRR. 2014. Understanding Risk - Review of Open Source and Open Access Software Packages Available to Quantify Risk from Natural Hazards. Available: <https://www.gfdr.org/en/publication/understanding-risk-review-open-source-and-open-access-software-packages-available> [Accessed July, 20, 2020].
- GRIMMOND, C. S. B., CLEUGH, H. A. & OKE, T. R. 1991. An objective urban heat storage model and its comparison with other schemes. *Atmospheric Environment. Part B. Urban Atmosphere*, 25, 311-326.
- GRIMMOND, C. S. B. & OKE, T. R. 2002. Turbulent heat fluxes in urban areas: Observations and a local-scale urban meteorological parameterization scheme (LUMPS). *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, 41, 792-810.
- HAMMOND, M. J., CHEN, A. S., DJORDJEVIĆ, S., BUTLER, D. & MARK, O. 2015. Urban flood impact assessment: A state-of-the-art review. *Urban Water Journal*, 12, 14-29.
- HEAVISIDE, C., MACINTYRE, H. & VARDOULAKIS, S. 2017. The urban heat island: implications for health in a changing environment. *Current environmental health reports*, 4, 296-305.
- HELFTER, C., TREMPER, A. H., HALIOS, C. H., KOTTHAUS, S., BJORKEGREN, A., GRIMMOND, C. S. B., BARLOW, J. F. & NEMITZ, E. 2016. Spatial and temporal variability of urban fluxes of methane, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide above London, UK. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 16, 10543--10557.
- HÉROUX, M.-E., ANDERSON, H. R., ATKINSON, R., BRUNEKREEF, B., COHEN, A., FORASTIERE, F., HURLEY, F., KATSOUYANNI, K., KREWSKI, D. & KRZYZANOWSKI, M. 2015. Quantifying the health impacts of ambient air pollutants: recommendations of a WHO/Europe project. *International journal of public health*, 60, 619-627.
- HERRERA-GOMEZ, S. S., QUEVEDO-NOLASCO, A. & PREZ-URRESTARAZU, L. 2017. The role of green roofs in climate change mitigation. A case study in Seville (Spain). *Building and Environment*, 123, 575--584.
- HLAVACOVA, I., KOLOMAZNIK, J. & LAZECKY, M. 2017. Ability of Sentinel-1 for monitoring structure displacements - case study of Ostrava bridges. FRINGE.
- IM, U., BRANDT, J., GEELS, C., HANSEN, K. M., CHRISTENSEN, J. H., ANDERSEN, M. S., SOLAZZO, E., KIOUSIOUKIS, I., ALYUZ, U. & BALZARINI, A. 2018. Assessment and economic valuation of air pollution impacts on human health over Europe and the United States as calculated by a multi-model ensemble in the framework of AQMEI13. *Atmospheric chemistry physics*, 18, 5967.
- IM, U., CHRISTENSEN, J. H., NIELSEN, O.-K., SAND, M., MAKKONEN, R., GEELS, C., ANDERSSON, C., KUKKONEN, J., LOPEZ-APARICIO, S. & BRANDT, J. 2019. Contributions of Nordic

- anthropogenic emissions on air pollution and premature mortality over the Nordic region and the Arctic. *Atmospheric Chemistry Physics*, 19, 12975-12992.
- ISO 1989. Hot Environments—Estimation of the Heat Stress on Working Man, Based on the WBGT-Index (Wet Bulb Globe Temperature). Geneva, Switzerland: International Standards Organisation.
- JAMES, S. L., ABATE, D., ABATE, K. H., ABAY, S. M., ABBAFATI, C., ABBASI, N., ABBASTABAR, H., ABD-ALLAH, F., ABDELA, J. & ABDELALIM, A. 2018. Global, regional, and national incidence, prevalence, and years lived with disability for 354 diseases and injuries for 195 countries and territories, 1990–2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *The Lancet*, 392, 1789-1858.
- JENSEN, S. S., BRANDT, J., CHRISTENSEN, J. H., GEELS, C., KETZEL, M., PLEJDRUP, M. S. & NIELSEN, O.-K. 2018. KORTLÆGNING AF LUFTFORURENINGENS HELBREDS-OG MILJØEFFEKTER I REGION HOVEDSTADEN: Videnskabelig rapport fra DCE–Nationalt Center for Miljø og Energi.
- JIANG, X. & YUNG, Y. L. 2019. Global Patterns of Carbon Dioxide Variability from Satellite Observations. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 47, 225--245.
- JIMENEZ-MUNOZ, J. C., SOBRINO, J. A., SKOKOVIC, D., MATTAR, C. & CRISTOBAL, J. 2014. Land surface temperature retrieval methods from landsat-8 thermal infrared sensor data. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 11, 1840--1843.
- KADAVERUGU, R., SHARMA, A., MATLI, C. & BINIWALE, R. 2019. High Resolution Urban Air Quality Modeling by Coupling CFD and Mesoscale Models: a Review. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 55, 539-556.
- KANDA, M., KANEGA, M., KAWAI, T., MORIWAKI, R. & SUGAWARA, H. 2007. Roughness lengths for momentum and heat derived from outdoor urban scale models. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 46, 1067-1079.
- KANG, J., TAN, J., JIN, R., LI, X. & ZHANG, Y. 2018. Reconstruction of MODIS land surface temperature products based on multi-temporal information. *Remote Sensing*, 10.
- KATO, S. & YAMAGUCHI, Y. 2007. Estimation of storage heat flux in an urban area using ASTER data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 110, 1-17.
- KENNEDY, C., STEINBERGER, J., GASSON, B., HANSEN, Y., HILLMAN, T., HAVRANEK, M., PATAKI, D., PHDUNGSILP, A., RAMASWAMI, A. & MENDEZ, G. V. 2010. Methodology for inventorying greenhouse gas emissions from global cities. *Energy Policy*, 38, 4828--4837.
- KHAN, J., KAKOSIMOS, K., RAASCHOU-NIELSEN, O., BRANDT, J., JENSEN, S. S., ELLERMANN, T. & KETZEL, M. 2019. Development and performance evaluation of new AirGIS—a GIS based air pollution and human exposure modelling system. *Atmospheric environment*, 198, 102-121.
- KLJUN, N., CALANCA, P., ROTACH, M. W. & SCHMID, H. P. 2015. A simple two-dimensional parameterisation for Flux Footprint Prediction (FFP). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 8, 3695--3713.
- KOLOMAZNIK, J. & HLAVACOVA, I. 2018. Project Report.
- KOLOMAZNIK, J. & IVANA, H. 2017. Project Report.

- KOTTHAUS, S., SMITH, T. E. L., WOOSTER, M. J. & GRIMMOND, C. S. B. 2014. Derivation of an urban materials spectral library through emittance and reflectance spectroscopy. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 94, 194--212.
- KUMAR, U., DE RIDDER, K., LEFEBVRE, W. & JANSSEN, S. 2012. Data assimilation of surface air pollutants (O₃ and NO₂) in the regional-scale air quality model AURORA. *Atmospheric Environment*, 60, 99-108.
- LANARI, R., MORA, O., MANUNTA, M., MALLORQUI, J. J., BERARDINO, P. & SANSOSTI, E. 2004. A small-baseline approach for investigating deformations on full-resolution differential SAR interferograms. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 42, 1377-1386.
- LAUWAET, D., DE NIJS, T., LIEKENS, I., HOOYBERGHS, H., VERACHTERT, E., LEFEBVRE, W., DE RIDDER, K., REMME, R. & BROEKX, S. 2018. A new method for fine-scale assessments of the average urban Heat island over large areas and the effectiveness of nature-based solutions. *One Ecosystem*, 3, e24880.
- LAUWAET, D., HOOYBERGHS, H., MAIHEU, B., LEFEBVRE, W., DRIESEN, G., VAN LOOY, S. & DE RIDDER, K. 2015. Detailed Urban Heat Island Projections for Cities Worldwide: Dynamical Downscaling CMIP5 Global Climate Models. 3, 391-415.
- LAUWAET, D., MAIHEU, B., DE RIDDER, K., BOËNNE, W., HOOYBERGHS, H., DEMUZERE, M. & VERDONCK, M.-L. 2020. A New Method to Assess Fine-Scale Outdoor Thermal Comfort for Urban Agglomerations. 8, 6.
- LAZECKÝ, M., JIRÁNKOVÁ, E. & BÖHMOVÁ, D. 2010. Usage of InSAR techniques to detect and monitor terrain subsidence due to mining activities.
- LEFEBVRE, W., VAN POPPEL, M., MAIHEU, B., JANSSEN, S. & DONS, E. 2013. Evaluation of the RIO-IFDM-street canyon model chain. *Atmospheric Environment*, 77, 325-337.
- LEFEBVRE, W., VERCAUTEREN, J., SCHROOTEN, L., JANSSEN, S., DEGRAEUWE, B., MAENHAUT, W., DE VLIAGER, I., VANKERKOM, J., COSEMANS, G., MENSINK, C., VELDEMAN, N., DEUTSCH, F., VAN LOOY, S., PEELAERTS, W. & LEFEBRE, F. 2011. Validation of the MIMOSA-AURORA-IFDM model chain for policy support: Modeling concentrations of elemental carbon in Flanders. *Atmospheric Environment*, 45, 6705-6713.
- LEFEBVRE, W. & VRANCKX, S. 2013. Validation of the IFDM-model for use in urban applications.
- LELIEVELD, J., KLINGMÜLLER, K., POZZER, A., PÖSCHL, U., FNAIS, M., DAIBER, A. & MÜNZEL, T. 2019. Cardiovascular disease burden from ambient air pollution in Europe reassessed using novel hazard ratio functions. *European heart journal*, 40, 1590-1596.
- LEMKE, B. & KJELLSTROM, T. 2012. Calculating Workplace WBGT from Meteorological Data: A Tool for Climate Change Assessment. *Industrial Health*, 50, 267-278.
- LEUNING, R. & KELLIHER, F. M. A. 1995. Leaf nitrogen, photosynthesis, conductance and transpiration: scaling from leaves to canopies. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 18, 1183-1200.
- LI, H., ZHOU, Y., LI, X., MENG, L., WANG, X., WU, S. & SODOUDI, S. 2018. A new method to quantify surface urban heat island intensity. *Science of The Total Environment*, 624, 262-272.

- LINDBERG, F., GRIMMOND, C. S. B., GABEY, A., HUANG, B., KENT, C. W., SUN, T., THEEUWES, N. E., JÄRVI, L., WARD, H. C., CAPEL-TIMMS, I., CHANG, Y., JONSSON, P., KRAVE, N., LIU, D., MEYER, D., OLOFSON, K. F. G., TAN, J., WÄSTBERG, D., XUE, L. & ZHANG, Z. 2018. Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor (UMEP): An integrated tool for city-based climate services. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 99, 70-87.
- LINDBERG, F., OLOFSON, K. F. G., SUN, T., GRIMMOND, C. S. B. & FEIGENWINTER, C. 2020. Urban storage heat flux variability explored using satellite, meteorological and geodata. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*.
- LIU, H. Z., FENG, J. W., JRVI, L. & VESALA, T. 2012. Four-year (2006-2009) eddy covariance measurements of CO₂ flux over an urban area in Beijing. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 12, 7881--7892.
- LIU, Y., MA, P., LIN, H., WANG, W. & SHI, G. 2019. Distributed Scatterer InSAR Reveals Surface Motion of the Ancient Chaoshan Residence Cluster in the Lianjiang Plain, China. 11, 166.
- LOGAN, T. M., ZAITCHIK, B., GUIKEMA, S. & NISBET, A. 2020. Night and day: The influence and relative importance of urban characteristics on remotely sensed land surface temperature. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 247.
- MANFREDA, S., SAMELA, C., SOLE, A. & FIORENTINO, M. 2014. Flood-Prone Areas Assessment Using Linear Binary Classifiers based on Morphological Indices. *Vulnerability, Uncertainty, and Risk*.
- MANFREDA, S., SOLE, A., LEO, M. D., MANFREDA, S., LEO, M. D. & SOLE, A. 2011. Detection of flood-prone areas using digital elevation models. *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering*, 781--790.
- MARCONCINI, M. & METZ, A. 2016a. A suite of novel EO-based products in support of urban green planning.
- MARCONCINI, M. & METZ, A. 2016b. A suite of novel EO-based products in support of urban green planning. 57--66.
- MARONGA, B., BANZHAF, S., BURMEISTER, C., ESCH, T., FORKEL, R., FRÖHLICH, D., FUKA, V., GEHRKE, K. F., GELETIČ, J., GIERSCH, S., GRONEMEIER, T., GROß, G., HELDENS, W., HELLSTEN, A., HOFFMANN, F., INAGAKI, A., KADASCH, E., KANANI-SÜHRING, F., KETELSEN, K., KHAN, B. A., KNIGGE, C., KNOOP, H., KRČ, P., KURPPA, M., MAAMARI, H., MATZARAKIS, A., MAUDER, M., PALLASCH, M., PAVLIK, D., PFAFFEROTT, J., RESLER, J., RISSMANN, S., RUSSO, E., SALIM, M., SCHREMPEF, M., SCHWENKEL, J., SECKMEYER, G., SCHUBERT, S., SÜHRING, M., VON TILS, R., VOLLMER, L., WARD, S., WITHA, B., WURPS, H., ZEIDLER, J. & RAASCH, S. 2020. Overview of the PALM model system 6.0. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 13, 1335-1372.
- MASSON, V. 2000. A Physically-Based Scheme For The Urban Energy Budget In Atmospheric Models. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 94, 357-397.
- MATGEN, P., MARTINIS, S., WAGNER, W., FREEMAN, V., ZEIL, P., MCCORMICK, N. & AND 2020. *Feasibility assessment of an automated, global, satellite-based flood monitoring product for the Copernicus Emergency Management Service*.
- MATHEW, A., KHANDELWAL, S. & KAUL, N. 2016. Spatial and temporal variations of urban heat island effect and the effect of percentage impervious surface area and elevation

- on land surface temperature: Study of Chandigarh city, India. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 26, 264-277.
- MEEHL, G. A. & TEBALDI, C. 2004. More Intense, More Frequent, and Longer Lasting Heat Waves in the 21st Century. 305, 994-997.
- MEEROW, S., NEWELL, J. P. & STULTS, M. 2016. Defining urban resilience: A review. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 147, 38-49.
- MEIJER Y. COPERNICUS CO2 TASK FORCE WITH SUB-TASK A, E. 2019. Copernicus Co2 Monitoring Mission Requirements Document. ESA.
- METZ, M., ROCCHINI, D. & NETELER, M. 2014. Surface temperatures at the continental scale: Tracking changes with remote sensing at unprecedented detail. *Remote Sensing*, 6, 3822--3840.
- MINDERHOUD, P. S., HLAVACOVA, I., KOLOMAZNIK, J. & NEUSSNER, O. 2020. Towards unraveling total subsidence of a mega-delta—the potential of new PS InSAR data for the Mekong delta. *Proceedings of the International Association of Hydrological Sciences*, 382, 327-332.
- MITRAKA, Z., CHRYSOULAKIS, N. & DOXANI, G. A. 2015. Urban surface temperature time series estimation at the local scale by spatial-spectral unmixing of satellite observations. *Remote Sensing*, 7, 4139--4156.
- MITRAKA, Z., CHRYSOULAKIS, N., KAMARIANAKIS, Y., PARTSINEVELO, P. & TSOUHLARAKI, A. 2012. Improving the estimation of urban surface emissivity based on sub-pixel classification of high resolution satellite imagery. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 117, 125--134.
- MITRAKA, Z. & DOXANI, G. A. 2016. Uncertainty Estimation of Local-Scale Land Surface Temperature Products over Urban Areas Using Monte Carlo Simulations. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 13, 917--921.
- MUELLER, N., ROJAS-RUEDA, D., BASAGAÑA, X., CIRACH, M., COLE-HUNTER, T., DADVAND, P., DONAIRE-GONZALEZ, D., FORASTER, M., GASCON, M. & MARTINEZ, D. 2017. Urban and transport planning related exposures and mortality: a health impact assessment for cities. *Environmental health perspectives*, 125, 89-96.
- NDOSSI, M. I. & AVDAN, U. 2016. Application of open source coding technologies in the production of Land Surface Temperature (LST) maps from Landsat: A PyQGIS plugin. *Remote Sensing*, 8.
- NIKOLOPOULOU, M. & LYKOURDIS, S. 2006. Thermal comfort in outdoor urban spaces: Analysis across different European countries. *Building and Environment*, 41, 1455-1470.
- NKWUNONWO, U. C., WHITWORTH, M. & BAILY, B. 2020. A review of the current status of flood modelling for urban flood risk management in the developing countries. *Scientific African*, 7.
- OCHOA-RODRÍGUEZ, S., ONOF, C. & MAKSIMOVIĆ, Č. 2013. Urban Pluvial Flood Modelling : Current Theory and Practice. 45.
- OFFERLE, B., GRIMMOND, C. S. B. & FORTUNIACK, K. 2005. Heat storage and anthropogenic heat flux in relation to the energy balance of a central European city centre. 25, 1405-1419.

- OSMANOĞLU, B., SUNAR, F., WADOWINSKI, S. & CABRAL-CANO, E. 2016. Time series analysis of InSAR data: Methods and trends. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry Remote Sensing*, 115, 90-102.
- OSWALD, S. M., HOLLOSI, B., UVELA-ALOISE, M., SEE, L., GUGGENBERGER, S., HAFNER, W., PROKOP, G., STORCH, A. & SCHIEDER, W. 2020. Using urban climate modelling and improved land use classifications to support climate change adaptation in urban environments: A case study for the city of Klagenfurt, Austria. *Urban Climate*, 31.
- PATRO, S., CHATTERJEE, C., MOHANTY, S., SINGH, R. & RAGHUWANSHI, N. S. 2009. Flood inundation modeling using MIKE FLOOD and remote sensing data. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, 37, 107--118.
- PEPE, A. & CALÒ, F. 2017. A review of interferometric synthetic aperture RADAR (InSAR) multi-track approaches for the retrieval of Earth's surface displacements. *Applied Sciences*, 7, 1264.
- PRIETO, I. A. 2017. A continuous deployment-based approach for the collaborative creation, maintenance, testing and deployment of cityGML models. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 32, 282--301.
- REHMAN, S., SAHANA, M., HONG, H., SAJJAD, H. & AHMED, B. B. 2019. A systematic review on approaches and methods used for flood vulnerability assessment: framework for future research. *Natural Hazards*, 96, 975-998.
- RIGHI, S., LUCIALLI, P. & POLLINI, E. 2009. Statistical and diagnostic evaluation of the ADMS-Urban model compared with an urban air quality monitoring network. *Atmospheric Environment*, 43, 3850-3857.
- RIGO, G. & PARLOW, E. 2007. Modelling the ground heat flux of an urban area using remote sensing data. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 90, 185-199.
- ROBERTS, S. M., OKE, T. R., GRIMMOND, C. S. B. & VOOGT, J. A. 2006. Comparison of four methods to estimate urban heat storage. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 45, 1766-1781.
- ROZENFELD, H. D., RYBSKI, D., GABAIX, X. & MAKSE, H. A. 2011. The Area and Population of Cities: New Insights from a Different Perspective on Cities %J American Economic Review. 101, 2205-25.
- SANTAMOURIS, M. 2020. Recent progress on urban overheating and heat island research. Integrated assessment of the energy, environmental, vulnerability and health impact. Synergies with the global climate change. *Energy Buildings*, 207, 109482.
- SANTIAGO, J. L., BORGE, R., MARTIN, F., DE LA PAZ, D., MARTILLI, A., LUMBRERAS, J. & SANCHEZ, B. 2017. Evaluation of a CFD-based approach to estimate pollutant distribution within a real urban canopy by means of passive samplers. *Science of the Total Environment*, 576, 46-58.
- SCHANZE, J. 2017. Nature-based solutions in flood risk management – Buzzword or innovation? 10, 281-282.
- SCHLAFFER, S., MATGEN, P., HOLLAUS, M. & WAGNER, W. 2015. Flood detection from multi-temporal SAR data using harmonic analysis and change detection. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 38, 15-24.

- SCHWARZ, N., LAUTENBACH, S. & SEPPELT, R. 2011. Exploring indicators for quantifying surface urban heat islands of European cities with MODIS land surface temperatures. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 115, 3175-3186.
- SCIFONI, S., BONANO, M., MARSELLA, M., SONNESSA, A., TAGLIAFIERRO, V., MANUNTA, M., LANARI, R., OJHA, C. & SCIOTTI, M. 2016. On the joint exploitation of long-term DInSAR time series and geological information for the investigation of ground settlements in the town of Roma (Italy). *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 182, 113-127.
- SOLARI, L., CIAMPALINI, A., RASPINI, F., BIANCHINI, S., ZINNO, I., BONANO, M., MANUNTA, M., MORETTI, S. & CASAGLI, N. 2017. Combined use of C-and X-Band SAR data for subsidence monitoring in an urban area. *Geosciences*, 7, 21.
- SOLARI, L., DEL SOLDATO, M., BIANCHINI, S., CIAMPALINI, A., EZQUERRO, P., MONTALTI, R., RASPINI, F. & MORETTI, S. 2018. From ERS 1/2 to Sentinel-1: subsidence monitoring in Italy in the last two decades. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 6, 149.
- SOMARAKIS, G. & STRATIGEA, A. 2019. Guiding informed choices on participation tools in spatial planning: An e-decision support system. *International Journal of E-Planning Research*, 8, 38-61.
- SORTSØ, C., EMNEUS, M., GREEN, A., JENSEN, P. B. & ERIKSSON, T. 2015. Societal costs of diabetes mellitus 2025 and 2040—Forecasts based on real world cost evidence and observed epidemiological trends in Denmark. *Modern Economy*, 6, 1150.
- SOSA, J., SAMPSON, C., SMITH, A., NEAL, J. & BATES, P. 2020. A toolbox to quickly prepare flood inundation models for LISFLOOD-FP simulations. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 123, 104561.
- STAGAKIS, S., CHRYSOULAKIS, N., SPYRIDAKIS, N., FEIGENWINTER, C. & VOGT, R. 2019. Eddy Covariance measurements and source partitioning of CO₂ emissions in an urban environment: Application for Heraklion, Greece. *Atmospheric Environment*, 201, 278--292.
- SULTANA, S. & SATYANARAYANA, A. N. V. 2020. Assessment of urbanisation and urban heat island intensities using landsat imageries during 2000 – 2018 over a sub-tropical Indian City. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 52.
- SUN, T., WANG, Z. H., OECHEL, W. C. & GRIMMOND, S. 2017. The Analytical Objective Hysteresis Model (AnOHM v1.0): Methodology to determine bulk storage heat flux coefficients. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10, 2875-2890.
- THORNLEY, J. H. M. & JOHNSON, I. R. 2000. *Plant and crop modelling: a mathematical approach to plant and crop physiology*.
- TOMÁS, R., ROMERO, R., MULAS, J., MARTURIÀ, J. J., MALLORQUÍ, J. J., LOPEZ-SANCHEZ, J. M., HERRERA, G., GUTIÉRREZ, F., GONZÁLEZ, P. J. & FERNÁNDEZ, J. 2014. Radar interferometry techniques for the study of ground subsidence phenomena: a review of practical issues through cases in Spain. *Environmental earth sciences*, 71, 163-181.
- UDALSAREA 2017. *Nature-based solutions for local climate adaptation in the Basque Country. Methodological guide for their identification and mapping. Klimatek Project 2016.*, Ihohe Environmental Management Agency; Ministry of the Environment Government Territorial Planning and Housing Basque Government.

- UN 2015. 2030 Agenda. United Nations.
- UN 2017. New Urban Agenda. United Nations.
- VOOGT, J. A. & GRIMMOND, C. S. B. 2000. Modeling surface sensible heat flux using surface radiative temperatures in a simple urban area. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, 39, 1679-1699.
- WANG, J., MENG, B., FU, D., PEI, T. & XU, C. 2018. Mapping spatiotemporal patterns and multi-perspective analysis of the surface urban heat islands across 32 major cities in China. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7.
- WARD, K., LAUF, S., KLEINSCHMIT, B. & ENDLICHER, W. 2016. Heat waves and urban heat islands in Europe: A review of relevant drivers. *Science of the Total Environment*, 569-570, 527--539.
- WELLMANN, T., SCHUG, F., HAASE, D., PFLUGMACHER, D. & VAN DER LINDEN, S. 2020. Green growth? On the relation between population density, land use and vegetation cover fractions in a city using a 30-years Landsat time series. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 202, 103857.
- WILLETT, K. M. & SHERWOOD, S. 2012. Exceedance of heat index thresholds for 15 regions under a warming climate using the wet-bulb globe temperature. 32, 161-177.
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION 2009a. Environment and health risks: the influence and effects of social inequalities: report of an expert group meeting, Bonn, Germany 9-10 September 2009. Copenhagen.: WHO Regional Office for Europe.
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION 2009b. EuroHEAT: Improving public health responses to extreme weather events/heat waves. Summary for policy makers. WHO Regional Office for Europe. Copenhagen.
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION 2009c. *Global health risks: mortality and burden of disease attributable to selected major risks*, World Health Organization.
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION 2013. Health risks of air pollution in Europe—HRAPIE project recommendations for concentration–response functions for cost–benefit analysis of particulate matter, ozone and nitrogen dioxide.
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION 2019. Preventing disease through healthy environments: exposure to highly hazardous pesticides: a major public health concern. World Health Organization.
- XU, N., LUO, J., ZUO, J., HU, X., DONG, J., WU, T., WU, S. & LIU, H. 2020. Accurate suitability evaluation of large-scale roof greening based on RS and GIS methods. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12.
- YANG, J., MENENTI, M., KRAYENHOFF, E. S., WU, Z., SHI, Q. & OUYANG, X. 2019. Parameterization of urban sensible heat flux from remotely sensed surface temperature: Effects of surface structure. *Remote Sensing*, 11.
- YANG, J., ZHOU, J., GTTSCHKE, F.-M., LONG, Z., MA, J. & LUO, R. 2020. Investigation and validation of algorithms for estimating land surface temperature from Sentinel-3 SLSTR data. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 91, 102136.

- ZHANG, T., FENG, P., MAKSIMOVIĆ, Č. & BATES, P. D. 2016. Application of a Three - Dimensional Unstructured - Mesh Finite - Element Flooding Model and Comparison with Two - Dimensional Approaches. *Water Resources Management*, 30, 823--841.
- ZHOU, B., RYBSKI, D. & KROPP, J. P. 2017. The role of city size and urban form in the surface urban heat island. *Scientific Reports*, 7, 4791.
- ZHOU, D., XIAO, J., BONAFONI, S., BERGER, C., DEILAMI, K., ZHOU, Y., FROLKING, S., YAO, R., QIAO, Z. & SOBRINO, J. A. 2019. Satellite remote sensing of surface urban heat islands: Progress, challenges, and perspectives. *Remote Sensing*, 11.
- ZHOU, X., CHANG, N.-B. & LI, S. 2009. Applications of SAR interferometry in earth and environmental science research. *Sensors*, 9, 1876-1912.